

TransformAr

Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in Europe:
demonstration of water-related innovation packages

Resilience Index (RI) for the mussel aquaculture operations in Galicia

Briefing on the development process of the RI solution and results

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon H2020 innovation action programme under grant agreement 101036683.

Work Package	WP4 – ACTIONABLE ADAPTIVE SOLUTIONS IMPLEMENTATION
Task	T4.2.2: RI - Resilience Index
Dissemination Level	Public
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Date	18 th July 2024

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This document has been prepared in the framework of the European project TransformAR. This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 innovation action programme under grant agreement no. 101036683.

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TRANSFORMAR PROJECT

The [TransformAr project](#), funded by the European Union's Horizon H2020 innovation action programme, aims to **accelerate transformational adaptation** in vulnerable regions across Europe. Coordinated by the University of Antwerp, TransformAr involves 22 partners from 11 European states. The project focuses on **developing and demonstrating solutions for large-scale adaptive processes**, utilizing open innovation, accessible climate data services, and actionable solutions. Through the implementation of Innovation Packages, TransformAr seeks to enhance communities' social and climate resilience.

MUSSEL AQUACULTURE IN GALICIA (SPAIN)

Within TransformAr's Work Package 4 (WP4), region-specific portfolios of adaptive solutions are being implemented in Key Community Systems (KCS) from six different countries. **Mussel aquaculture** in Galicia (Spain) has been identified as one of those sensitive KCS, as it plays a vital role in the economic well-being of the region, providing employment opportunities and supporting socio-economic development, while facing significant risks from extreme weather events induced by climate change.

RESILIENCE INDEX

This report describes the development methodology of a **Resilience Index (RI)** for the operations of the mussel farming in the Ría de Arousa (Arousa Estuary) in Galicia. This index, developed by the [REDE research group from the University of Vigo](#), aims to guide stakeholders' behavioural change and provide policymakers and value chain actors with strategic insights to adapt mussel farming operations to extreme climate change effects.

The RI has also potential applications in other sectors and regions facing similar challenges. By promoting behavioural change and adaptation measures, the aim is to mitigate operational risks and enhance the resilience of vulnerable communities and industries across Europe.

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The region of Galicia, located in the northwest of Spain, is known for its coastal inlets known as "Rías" which present favourable conditions for mussel aquaculture in hanging rafts. In particular, the **Ría de Arousa is the largest and most productive** in Galicia with 70% of the mussel rafts.

This Galician estuary also faces climatic vulnerabilities that pose threats to the productive sector and regional stability. In order to adapt to this scenario, two solutions are being developed within the framework of TransformAr. On the one hand, **CETMAR**, coordinator of the Galician demonstrator in TransformAr, will **monitor climate variables in real time for mussel rafts**. On the other hand, the **University of Vigo has developed the Resilience Index**, the subject of this report, to guide strategic decisions to avoid interruptions in production operations.

MUSSEL RAFTS

RÍA DE AROUSA

GALICIA

EUROPE

Figure 1. Galicia demonstrator

At its essence, the Resilience Index is a mathematical model that provides an exhaustive assessment about the adaptation capacity of the operative processes to the effects of climate change (the dashboard above is presented in detail in Section 7).

Rather than focus on a specific aspect, it assesses in a comprehensive manner how effectively a system can manage the challenges posed by climate change. It resembles a thorough health assessment for adaptation capacity, considering risk scenarios, and resilience factors within productive processes.

Figure 2. The Resilience Index as a decision-making assistance tool

Figure 3. Resilience index simplified development process

In general terms, the methodology for the development of the RI employs a hybrid methodology that integrates climate data and scenarios with input from experts and stakeholders. It unfolds **3 phases**:

- First, will be necessary to **identify experts and stakeholders** and to collect and model the necessary information on the value chain, climatic variables & projections, and resilience factors for adaptation.
- Secondly, two **expert and stakeholders' consultations under Delphi method** will be conducted to set up a prioritization to define vulnerabilities, risks and resilience factors in the value chain.
- Finally, along with the **adaptation capacities assessment** of the key resilience factors in the sector, **the Resilience index will be defined and calculated.**

The recommendations derived from the RI will provide specific insights that allow to define **actions and a roadmap to improve resilience.**

In the next page, a more detailed scheme of the process is presented.

Figure 4. Resilience Index development process

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In order to develop the actions of the second phase of the RI methodology, which will lead to the identification of the variables of the RI mathematical model, some context and background information was needed to be identified in advance.

Through literature review and expert consultation, three main documents have been developed. From left to right:

- Contextualization document
- Identification of production stages of the mussel aquaculture processes
- Identification of resilience factors for climate change adaptation

These documents are in **Spanish** as they have been distributed among local experts contributing to the participatory dynamics of the second phase of the RI development methodology.

The following pages detail the content of each of these documents.

Figure 5. Context and background documents

Every document has been reviewed by a panel of 5 experts with expertise in the mussel aquaculture, resilience and/or adaptation to climate change.

Figure 6. Contextualization document

The purpose of this document is to provide an **overview of the context of the mussel sector in Galicia**, in order to provide complementary information that may be **useful for the completion of the first consultation to experts (Delphi 1 questionnaire)**. The key aspects that make up the environment in which this important aquaculture activity takes place are presented:

- Geographic context
- The climate of the territory
- Demographic context
- Socio-economic context
- Business and R+D+I context
- Institutional framework

Figure 7. Document on the stages of the mussel farming process

The objective of this report was to identify and validate the main stages of the mussel farming process identified through literature review, from the mussel seed collection to the depuration. After revision by experts, **nine phases of the production process were identified and validated.** In addition, Sanitary Controls have been identified as a cross-cutting activity in all these phases.

Once these phases were validated, were used as reference during **Delphi 1** consultation, detailed further ahead in this report.

By analysing key processes in the production process, it was possible to assess and measure the sector's adaptive capacity and response, providing a solid basis for informed decision-making and the implementation of appropriate mitigation and adaptation measures.

Figure 7. Stages of the mussel farming process

Figure 8. Resilience factors document

The objective of this document was to **present and validate a list of resilience factors**, identified through literature review, and related to the adaptation of mussel aquaculture to the adverse effects of climate change.

In the next page, a more detailed description of the resilience factors is provided.

Stakeholder validation of this list ensured that the resilience factors identified are sufficiently relevant and accurate to be integrated into the design of the **Delphi 2** questionnaire. In this query, the expert panel responded indicating the extent to which each of the resilience factors contributed to minimizing the risks of each of the identified scenarios in Delphi 1.

Dimension	Resilience Factor
1. Governance	1.1 Training programs
	1.2 Flexible management
	1.3 Marine spatial planning
	1.4 Management of public-private funds
2. R+D+i	2.1 Advanced scientific research
	2.2 Improvement of exposure forecasts
	2.3 Applied biotechnology projects
	2.4 Development of new technologies
3. Risk management	3.1 Multitrophic aquaculture
	3.2 Adapted insurance coverage
	3.3 Ecosystem Approaches to Aquaculture (EEA)
	3.4 Emergency action plans
4. Collaboration	4.1 Intersectoral collaboration
	4.2 Interdisciplinary cooperation
	4.3 International cooperation networks
	4.4 Intra-sectoral collaboration
5. Operational environment	5.1 Adaptation of infrastructures
	5.2 Monitoring and warning systems
	5.3 Improvement of production techniques
	5.4 Flexible procedures

Table 1. Resilience factors for adaptation in the mussel aquaculture sector

Dimension	Resilience Factor description
1. GOVERNANCE	<p>1.1 Training programs: Joint training initiatives aimed at regulatory authorities, the productive sector and other key agents on the challenges of climate change and maritime culture to provide them with tools and knowledge to implement effective adaptation strategies.</p> <p>1.2 Flexible management: Use of adaptive management principles, both by the public administration and the productive sector, to address uncertainty with a flexible and agile approach (e.g. iterative decision-making, incorporation of constant feedback and adjustment of assumptions according to the evolution of the scenarios).</p> <p>1.3 Marine spatial planning: Introduce into Maritime Spatial Planning Plans (MSPs) strategies that incorporate the assessment of potential impacts of climate change on mussel aquaculture and other maritime activities, with the aim of preventing conflicts and promoting sustainable coexistence between various sectors.</p> <p>1.4 Management of public-private funds: Assessment of the financial needs for the adaptation of the sector in order to efficiently create and manage funds of public-private origin that allow preventive actions to be carried out and/or to cover future contingencies.</p>
2. R+D+I	<p>2.1 Advanced scientific research: Development of specific innovative studies aimed at identifying patterns, projecting future scenarios and deepening the understanding of the impacts of climate change on the production process for informed decision-making based on scientific evidence.</p> <p>2.2 Improvement of exposure forecasts: Use of models to predict changes in the frequency and intensity of oceanic-meteorological variables to anticipate the level of exposure of each cultivation area, minimizing risks and improving the capacity to act.</p> <p>2.3 Applied biotechnology projects: Promotion of biotechnology applications aimed at the development of mussel strains that are more resistant to stressors associated with climate change, such as extreme weather events or increased frequency of toxic tides. This includes strategies such as selective breeding, genomic selection to preserve robustness, or genetic adaptation, among others.</p> <p>2.4 Development of new technologies: Development and implementation of advanced technological solutions that have innovative processes to promote flexibility, better environmental control and greater efficiency in the use of resources in a changing environment (e.g. smart buoys, remote sensors, drones or artificial intelligence-based systems for early warning).</p>
3. RISK MANAGEMENT	<p>3.1 Multitrophic aquaculture: Diversification of production through the identification and use of possible synergies with species that are more resilient to climate change and extensive farming (macroalgae, crustaceans, etc.).</p> <p>3.2 Adapted insurance coverage: Underwriting insurance policies that provide adequate coverage for potential risks arising from climate change, in situations where it is not possible to take preventive measures.</p> <p>3.3 Ecosystem Approaches to Aquaculture (EEA): Strategies for integrating aquaculture into the context of the wider ecosystem in which it takes place, reducing disaster risk while promoting sustainable development, equity and resilience of interconnected socio-ecological systems.</p> <p>3.4 Emergency action plans: Design contingency plans with agile and predefined responses, adapted to extreme weather events, which help coordinate the authorities, the productive sector and other actors in order to minimize impacts and losses.</p>
4. COLLABORATION	<p>4.1 Intersectoral collaboration: Partnership with other actors in the productive sector, with the extractive fishing sector and with other complementary sectors for joint negotiation and alignment of actions in the face of possible risks.</p> <p>4.2 Interdisciplinary cooperation: Clear and accessible channels of communication between agents from different disciplines (biology, engineering, climatology, economics, administration, etc.) with the aim of seeking comprehensive solutions and coordinating adaptation measures to the impacts of climate change.</p> <p>4.3 International cooperation networks: Participation of sector actors in international cooperation networks to share information, resources, best practices and experiences on adaptation.</p> <p>4.4 Intra-sectoral collaboration: Creation of collaborative networks in which each cultivation area specializes in a specific phase of the production process, depending on the optimal climatic and meteorological conditions for that specific stage. E.g., some farming areas may focus on mussel farming, while others may specialize in fattening.</p>
5. OPERATIONAL ENVIRONMENT	<p>5.1 Adaptation of infrastructures: Incorporation of new infrastructure, improvements to existing assets and nature-based solutions (e.g. creation of artificial reefs, integrated mariculture, restoration of seagrass meadows, etc.) focused on increasing resilience to the impacts of climate change on the aquaculture process.</p> <p>5.2 Monitoring and warning systems: Adoption of real-time monitoring and early warning systems that allow the monitoring of farm conditions, agile response to adverse events and changing conditions (oceanic-meteorological phenomena, pests, predators, etc.).</p> <p>5.3 Improvement of production techniques: Adoption of technology monitoring processes aimed at identifying the best available practices, as well as the development and incorporation of innovative techniques and solutions that strengthen the adaptation of operations to the challenges of climate change</p> <p>5.4 Flexible procedures: Operating procedures, based on the principles of continuous improvement and the circular economy, with the ability to adapt to changing conditions and new production needs that allow a better use of both resources and products, in a sustainable cycle.</p>

Table 2. Resilience factors in detail

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Figure 9. Delphi 1 development process.

WHAT DOES IT CONSIST OF?

“The Delphi method was developed by RAND in the 1950s to forecast the effect of technology on warfare. It has since been applied to health care, education, management, and environmental science. Today, groups of experts or stakeholders use online tools to anonymously answer questionnaires, receive feedback that represents the “group response,” discuss, and revise their answers to see whether they can approach expert consensus.” (RAND Corporation, 2024)¹.

WHAT DOES IT CONSIST OF?

The expert panel, composed of stakeholders related to the mussel sector, resilience and climate change, will participate in **2 Delphi dynamics**, composed of **three rounds each**.

Only responses from experts who have participated in all three rounds will be considered valid.

¹RAND Corporation (2024). Delphi Method. Retrieved from <https://www.rand.org/topics/delphi-method.html>, March 15th, 2024.

Delphi 1

In the **first Delphi**, the objective was that the experts assess the extent to which each of the climatic and ocean-meteorological elements provided (sea level rise, increase in rainfall, etc.) affects each of the selected phases of the production process (Seed collection, Fattening, Declumping, etc.).

The intersection of both terms gave rise to the definition of **risk scenarios**, evaluated by assigning a score between 0 and 3, with 0 being "no effect at all" and 3 being "high effect". This consultation was conducted using an online form.

After receiving the responses, aggregation of the answers was carried out by statistical analysis. This result was shared with the experts prior to the start of the next round. This process is repeated in the third and final round. This first Delphi resulted in a ranking of the scenarios according to their level of risk and fed into the second Delphi.

Delphi 2

The process followed in **Delphi 2** was analogous to Delphi 1. However, the focus shifted to assess the degree to which each proposed resilience factor within the mussel sector contributes to addressing the identified risk scenarios from the Delphi 1. The results of this dynamic made possible to prioritize the **resilience factors** and **resilience gaps** existing in the sector.

The process and results of each Delphi consultation are presented in more detail in the next sections.

In order to identify the experts taking part in the Delphi method, different groups of stakeholders related to the mussel aquaculture in Ría de Arousa were considered. The definition of those groups was developed using as conceptual framework the **innovation model of the quintuple helix** from Carayannis & Campbell (2020)¹.

This model represents **the most comprehensive version** to the date, encompassing the Triple Helix (relating to the interplay between academia, industry, and government), the fourth helix from the Quadruple Helix model (media-based and culture-based public) and an additional helix on the “natural environments of society”.

Thanks to the support and expertise of CETMAR, a preliminary stakeholder database was developed, which includes more than 60 organizations in the case study. However, in the Delphi method studies indicate that a **minimum of 7 and not more than 30 experts is optimal**.

Figure 10. Quintuple Helix framework

¹Carayannis, E. G., & Campbell, D. F. (2010). Triple Helix, Quadruple Helix and Quintuple Helix and how do knowledge, innovation and the environment relate to each other?: a proposed framework for a trans-disciplinary analysis of sustainable development and social ecology. *International Journal of Social Ecology and Sustainable Development (IJSESD)*, 1(1), 41-69.

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Stakeholder groups	Experts
Science / Academia	4
Government	4
Society	5
Environment	4
Economy	6
	23

Gender	Total	%
Men	12	52,17%
Women	11	47,83%
	23	100%

The objective of constructing a Resilience Index requires the identification of the **key players involved in the case study region**, specifically, those with knowledge and expertise about resilience, climate change and socioeconomic aspects of the Key Community System of the mussel aquaculture in Galicia. Hence, while this work does not strive to provide an exhaustive list, it aims to include a representative sample of the stakeholders relevant to the project.

According to the participant thresholds accepted for the Delphi method (7-30 experts), for Delphi 1 a total of **34 experts have been invited**, of which **23 have been engaged to complete their participation in all three rounds**. These 23 experts were distributed in a well-balanced proportion among the five stakeholder groups.

In terms of gender, we also observe a **distribution very close to full parity**.

Table 3. Expert panel distribution in Delphi 1

Esto es una encuesta previa y no se guardarán los resultados.

ÍNDICE DE RESILIENCIA OPERATIVA DEL CULTIVO DEL MEJILLÓN

Formulario Delphi 1 (Ronda 1)

La metodología Delphi nos permitirá recopilar y analizar conocimientos y opiniones del panel de expertos del que forma parte, con más de 20 actores vinculados al sector mejillonero, a ámbito académico, a agentes sociales, a la administración y al medioambiente.

Tras tres rondas de este cuestionario, se busca obtener consenso y conclusiones robustas basadas en el intercambio de ideas para la identificación de escenarios de riesgo para el proceso productivo del mejillón en Galicia.

Sólo necesitará unos minutos para completar este cuestionario y todas sus respuestas serán privadas y confidenciales.

El plazo para completar esta primera ronda finalizará el jueves 6 de julio de 2023, a las 14:00 h. Ante cualquier duda o aclaración que necesite, puede contactar con el equipo TransformAr-Galicia en el e-mail transformar@uvigo.gal o el teléfono 986 130 108.

A continuación, se muestra una matriz que, en las filas contrasta datos históricos con proyecciones futuras de variables climáticas y oceánico-meteorológicas, consideradas como las más relevantes por los expertos consultados, en relación con su impacto en la acuicultura del mejillón. En las columnas se detallan las fases clave del proceso de producción del mejillón, desde la recogida de la mejilla hasta la depuración.

* 1. Puntúe, empleando una escala entre 0 y 3, en qué medida pueden afectar negativamente los siguientes elementos climáticos y oceánico-meteorológicos (y su variación) a cada una de las fases del proceso productivo del mejillón en la Ría de Arousa. Si lo desea, puede añadir comentarios adicionales en la pregunta 2.

Siendo 0 = No se considera afectación negativa; 1 = Afectación negativa baja; 2 = Afectación negativa media; 3 = Afectación negativa alta

Tenga en cuenta que algunas proyecciones se presentan con un horizonte temporal que abarca hasta 2050, mientras que otras se extienden hasta el año 2100. Esta variación en el horizonte temporal está determinada por el grado de significatividad de cada proyección.

	Obtención de mejilla de cuerdas	Obtención de la mejilla de la zona de roca	Encordado	Preengorde	Desdoble	Engorde	Cosecha	envasado	depuradora	Depuración
--	---------------------------------	--	-----------	------------	----------	---------	---------	----------	------------	------------

Temperatura del Aire:
Para el período 2011-2020 la temperatura media anual del aire en Vilanova de Arousa fue de 15,1°C y hubo un promedio de 40 días cálidos por año (temperatura máxima superior a 26°C). Para 2050 se espera que la temperatura media del aire sea de 16,6°C, y que tengamos un promedio aproximado de 60 días cálidos por año.

Temperatura superficial del agua:
Durante el período 2011-2020 hubo un promedio de 49 días/año con temperatura máxima superficial del agua superior a 20°C en la zona interna de la Ría de Arousa y de 10 días/año en la zona externa. Para 2050 se espera un promedio de 59 días/año con temperatura máxima superior a 20°C en la zona interna de la ría y de 14 días/año en la zona externa.

Precipitación:
Durante el período 2011-2020, en la Ría de Arousa hubo 6,2 días de lluvia extrema al año (superior a 33,8 litros/m² acumulado diario). Para el período 2071-2100, se esperan 8,2 días de lluvia extrema, si bien el incremento se concentrará en el invierno y disminuirá en verano.

Nivel del mar:
Durante el período 1945-2015, el nivel del mar ha subido 20 cm, con una tasa de incremento de 2,4 cm/década. Para 2050, el nivel medio del mar subirá entre 15-35 cm y para 2100 habrá subido entre 0,5m y 1m. Esto supone un incremento medio de un 9,8 cm por década desde el año 2020.

Nota: Con cada centímetro de subida del nivel del mar se pierden entre 0,6 - 1 m de arena!

Afloramiento:
Durante el período 2011-2020, el volumen medio de agua que afloró en la Ría de Arousa (índice de afloramiento) durante Abril-Septiembre (semestre favorable al afloramiento) fue de 440 m³/skm de costa. Para 2050, se espera un valor medio del índice de afloramiento de 480 m³/skm de costa para el mismo semestre (incremento medio de 11,25 m³/skm de costa por década).

Viento:
Durante el período 2011-2020 hubo una media de 35 días/año con viento de fuerza 6 o superior (velocidad superior a 45 km/h) en la zona exterior de la ría y una media de 1 día/año en la zona interior. Para 2050 se espera que los vientos de fuerza 6 estén presentes durante 50 días/año en la zona exterior. No se esperan vientos de esa intensidad en la zona interna.

Acidificación:
Durante el período 1980-2020 se ha observado una disminución del pH/década en la Ría de Arousa de 8,15 a 8,05 unidades en la zona externa, y de 8,10 a 7,95 unidades en la interna. En 2050 se esperan valores de 7,95 (exterior) y 7,85 (interior) y para 2100 se prevé que el pH caiga hasta 7,8 (exterior) y 7,7 (interior), próximos al umbral en el que resulta corrosivo para la concha del mejillón y otros bivalvos (aprox. 7,6 unidades).

Nota: Una caída de pH en 0,3 unidades significa duplicar la acidez del agua.

2. Si lo desea, puede añadir cualquier comentario o aclaración que considere relevante sobre el contenido de la matriz que ha cubierto.

3. Consentimiento informado

- Estoy conforme con las siguientes afirmaciones:
- Acepto participar en este estudio.
 - Entiendo que la participación en este estudio es voluntaria.
 - Confirmando que he leído y comprendido la información previa facilitada para este estudio.
 - Entiendo que mis datos se utilizarán de forma anónima.

Finalizar

Funciona con [CheckMarket](#)

The online questionnaire was developed in the platform Medallia (formerly CheckMarket) and in Spanish for a better understanding by local experts.

The description of all the items in the form can be read in English in page 28. In addition, all the results in this report are presented in English.

Figure 12. Delphi 1 online questionnaire

Figure 13. Risk scenarios matrix from the Delphi 1 online questionnaire

The questionnaire showed a matrix that, in the rows, contrasts **historical data with future projections of climatic and oceanic-meteorological variables**, considered as the most relevant by the experts consulted, in relation to their impact on mussel aquaculture. The columns detail the **key stages of the mussel production process**, identified and validated in the first phase of the RI development methodology.

The climatic variables have been described with the collaboration of the [Instituto de Investigaciones Mariñas](#) (IIM-CSIC) and [CETMAR](#).

The experts had to score all the intersections of both terms in a **scale between 0 and 3**, with 0 being "no effect at all" and 3 being "high effect". The results will show the **priority risk scenarios**.

RESULTS FROM DELPHI 1 ONLINE QUESTIONNAIRE

23 experts

70 risk scenarios assessed

13 risk scenarios prioritized

04 DELPHI 1: RISK SCENARIOS - RESULTS

Matrix of results by expert (1/2)

Risk scenarios selected for Delphi 2 (C.V. ≤ 0,5, Mean ≥ 1,5)

RISK SCENARIO	EXPERT																							Mean	Mode	Media	Std.	C.V. ⁽²⁾
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23					
1. Air temperature/Seed collection from collecting ropes	0	0	0	1	1	0	3	1	1	0	1	2	3	3	1	1	3	1	1	2	0	2	0	1,17	1	1	1,07	0,91
2. Air temperature/Seed collection from the rock	3	1	0	2	1	1	3	2	1	2	2	2	3	3	2	2	3	1	1	3	2	2	1	1,87	2	2	0,87	0,46
3. Air temperature/Seed tubing	1	1	0	2	1	1	3	2	1	0	2	2	3	3	1	1	2	0	1	3	0	0	1	1,35	1	1	1,03	0,76
4. Air temperature/Pre-fattening	0	0	0	1	1	0	3	1	0	0	0	2	3	3	1	1	2	0	1	3	0	1	0	1,00	0	1	1,13	1,13
5. Air temperature/Declumping and thinning	1	1	0	1	1	1	2	2	1	0	2	2	3	3	1	1	2	1	1	3	0	2	1	1,39	1	1	0,89	0,64
6. Air temperature/Fattening	0	0	0	1	1	0	2	1	0	0	0	2	3	3	1	1	2	1	1	3	0	2	0	1,04	0	1	1,07	1,02
7. Air temperature/Harvesting	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	3	2	1	1	1	0	1	3	1	1	1	1,17	1	1	0,72	0,61
8. Air temperature/Cleaning, declumping and grading	1	0	0	3	1	2	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0,70	1	1	0,76	1,10
9. Air temperature/Register and transport to depuration	1	0	0	3	1	2	0	1	0	0	1	1	2	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	0	1	1	0,74	1	1	0,81	1,10
10. Air temperature/Depuration	0	0	0	2	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0,48	0	0	0,59	1,24
11. Superficial water temperature/Seed collection from collecting ropes	3	1	2	3	2	1	3	3	2	2	2	3	3	3	2	1	3	1	3	3	2	2	2	2,26	3	2	0,75	0,33
12. Superficial water temperature/Seed collection from the rock	3	1	2	3	2	2	3	2	2	2	2	3	3	3	2	2	3	1	3	3	2	2	2	2,30	2	2	0,63	0,28
13. Superficial water temperature/Seed tubing	1	0	1	3	1	0	3	1	1	0	0	3	3	3	1	1	2	0	2	3	0	0	1	1,30	1	1	1,18	0,91
14. Superficial water temperature/Pre-fattening	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	3	3	3	2	1	2	1	2	3	1	3	2	1,96	2	2	0,71	0,36
15. Superficial water temperature/Declumping and thinning	1	1	2	2	1	1	2	1	1	0	0	3	3	3	1	1	2	2	2	3	0	3	1	1,57	1	1	0,99	0,63
16. Superficial water temperature/Fattening	2	2	2	3	2	1	2	3	2	1	2	3	3	3	2	1	2	0	3	3	1	3	2	2,09	2	2	0,85	0,41
17. Superficial water temperature/Harvesting	1	1	2	3	2	0	1	2	1	1	0	3	3	2	2	1	1	1	3	3	1	1	2	1,61	1	1	0,94	0,58
18. Superficial water temperature/Cleaning, declumping and grading	0	0	0	3	1	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0,52	0	0	0,73	1,40
19. Superficial water temperature/Register and transport to depuration	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	0,39	0	0	0,72	1,85
20. Superficial water temperature/Depuration	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	2	1	0,70	1	1	0,76	1,10
21. Rainfall/Seed collection from collecting ropes	1	1	1	1	1	0	3	1	1	1	2	3	2	3	1	1	2	0	0	3	1	1	1	1,35	1	1	0,93	0,69
22. Rainfall/Seed collection from the rock	2	0	1	2	1	2	3	2	1	1	2	3	2	3	2	1	2	0	0	3	1	3	1	1,65	2	2	0,98	0,59
23. Rainfall/Seed tubing	1	0	0	1	0	0	3	1	1	0	1	3	3	3	1	1	2	1	0	3	0	3	1	1,26	1	1	1,18	0,93
24. Rainfall/Pre-fattening	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	0	2	3	3	3	1	1	2	2	0	3	0	3	1	1,57	1	1	0,99	0,63
25. Rainfall/Declumping and thinning	1	1	1	1	1	0	2	1	1	0	1	3	3	3	1	1	2	2	0	3	0	2	1	1,35	1	1	0,98	0,73
26. Rainfall/Fattening	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	0	2	3	3	3	1	1	2	2	0	3	0	1	1	1,48	1	1	0,95	0,64
27. Rainfall/Harvesting	2	1	0	2	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	3	3	1	0	1	1	2	0	3	0	1	1	1,13	1	1	0,97	0,86
28. Rainfall/Cleaning, declumping and grading	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	1	2	0	1	0	0	2	0,48	0	0	0,73	1,53
29. Rainfall/Register and transport to depuration	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	2	0	0	0	1	2	0	1	0	0	1	0,39	0	0	0,66	1,68
30. Rainfall/Depuration	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	1	2	0	1	1	1	2	0	0	0	1	1	0,57	0	0	0,73	1,29
31. Sea level/Seed collection from collecting ropes	0	1	1	1	0	0	3	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	2	0	0	2	0	0	0	0,70	0	1	0,82	1,18
32. Sea level/Seed collection from the rock	2	2	1	3	2	3	3	2	1	1	3	1	3	1	2	2	2	0	0	2	1	2	2	1,78	2	2	0,90	0,51
33. Sea level/Seed tubing	0	1	0	1	0	0	3	1	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	1	0,61	0	0	0,78	1,29
34. Sea level/Pre-fattening	0	1	0	1	0	0	3	1	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	0,61	0	0	0,78	1,29
35. Sea level/Declumping and thinning	0	1	0	1	0	0	2	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	0	2	0	0	1	0,57	0	0	0,66	1,17

Table 4. Matrix of results by expert (1/2)

(1) Standard deviation: this is used to determine the dispersion of the data in its distribution with respect to the mean. The lower the value, the more clustered the data will be around the sample mean.

(2) C.V. = Coefficient of variation. Ratio between the standard deviation and the sample mean. In our case, we use it to estimate the degree of agreement between the answers of the different experts. The lower the value of the coefficient of variation, the greater the concordance in the answers.

04 DELPHI 1: RISK SCENARIOS - RESULTS

Matrix of results by expert (2/2)

Risk scenarios selected for Delphi 2 (C.V. ≤ 0,5, Mean ≥ 1,5)

RISK SCENARIO	EXPERT																							Mean	Mode	Media	Std.	C.V. ⁽²⁾
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23					
36. Sea level/Fattening	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	0,48	0	0	0,59	1,24
37. Sea level/Harvesting	0	1	0	2	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	1	0,48	0	0	0,67	1,39
38. Sea level/Cleaning, declumping and grading	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0,22	0	0	0,42	1,94
39. Sea level/Register and transport to depuration	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0,17	0	0	0,39	2,23
40. Sea level/Depuration	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0,22	0	0	0,42	1,94
41. Upwelling/Seed collection from collecting ropes	0	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	0	3	0	3	3	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	1,00	0	1	1,09	1,09
42. Upwelling/Seed collection from the rock	0	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	0	3	0	3	3	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	1,09	0	1	1,04	0,96
43. Upwelling/Seed tubing	0	1	1	0	1	0	2	1	0	0	0	0	3	3	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0,65	0	0	0,93	1,43
44. Upwelling/Pre-fattening	0	1	1	0	2	2	1	2	1	0	3	0	3	3	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0,91	0	1	1,08	1,19
45. Upwelling/Declumping and thinning	0	0	1	0	2	2	1	1	0	0	0	0	3	3	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0,70	0	0	0,97	1,40
46. Upwelling/Fattening	0	1	1	0	2	3	0	2	1	0	3	0	3	3	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0,91	0	0	1,16	1,28
47. Upwelling/Harvesting	0	1	1	0	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	3	2	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0,52	0	0	0,85	1,62
48. Upwelling/Cleaning, declumping and grading	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0,26	0	0	0,69	2,64
49. Upwelling/Register and transport to depuration	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	1	0,13	0	0	0,34	2,64
50. Upwelling/Depuration	0	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0,22	0	0	0,52	2,38
51. Wind/Seed collection from collecting ropes	1	1	0	1	2	1	2	2	1	0	3	1	3	3	1	1	2	1	1	2	0	1	0	1,30	1	1	0,93	0,71
52. Wind/Seed collection from the rock	1	1	0	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	3	3	2	1	2	2	1	2	1	2	1	1,57	1	2	0,73	0,46
53. Wind/Seed tubing	1	1	0	2	2	1	2	2	1	1	2	1	3	3	1	1	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	1,48	1	1	0,73	0,49
54. Wind/Pre-fattening	1	1	0	1	2	0	1	1	1	0	3	1	2	3	1	1	1	1	1	2	0	1	0	1,09	1	1	0,85	0,78
55. Wind/Declumping and thinning	1	1	0	3	2	1	0	2	1	1	1	1	2	3	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	1,30	1	1	0,76	0,59
56. Wind/Fattening	1	1	0	1	2	1	0	1	1	1	3	1	2	3	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	0	1,17	1	1	0,78	0,66
57. Wind/Harvesting	1	2	1	2	2	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	1,26	1	1	0,54	0,43
58. Wind/Cleaning, declumping and grading	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	0	0	1	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0,43	0	0	0,59	1,36
59. Wind/Register and transport to depuration	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	0	1	0,26	0	0	0,54	2,07
60. Wind/Depuration	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0,17	0	0	0,49	2,82
61. Acidification/Seed collection from collecting ropes	3	1	1	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	3	3	3	3	2	3	2	3	2	3	2	3	2	2,52	3	3	0,67	0,26
62. Acidification/Seed collection from the rock	3	1	1	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	3	3	3	3	2	3	2	3	2	3	2	3	2	2,52	3	3	0,67	0,26
63. Acidification/Seed tubing	2	1	1	3	2	0	3	2	1	1	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	2	3	1	3	1	2,00	2	2	0,90	0,45
64. Acidification/Pre-fattening	3	1	1	3	3	3	3	2	2	1	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	3	2	3	1	3	2	2,35	3	3	0,78	0,33
65. Acidification/Declumping and thinning	2	1	1	3	3	1	2	2	1	1	3	3	3	3	2	1	2	2	2	3	1	3	1	2,00	1	2	0,85	0,43
66. Acidification/Fattening	3	1	1	3	3	2	1	2	2	1	3	3	3	3	2	1	2	3	2	3	1	3	2	2,17	3	2	0,83	0,38
67. Acidification/Harvesting	2	1	1	3	3	1	1	1	1	1	3	3	3	1	2	1	2	3	2	3	1	3	2	1,91	1	2	0,90	0,47
68. Acidification/Cleaning, declumping and grading	1	0	0	3	0	0	0	1	0	0	3	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	2	1	0,70	0	0	1,02	1,47
69. Acidification/Register and transport to depuration	1	0	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	3	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	1	0	2	1	0,61	0	0	0,89	1,46
70. Acidification/Depuration	0	0	1	3	0	0	0	1	0	0	3	0	2	0	0	0	1	0	0	2	0	2	0	0,65	0	0	1,03	1,58

Table 5. Matrix of results by expert (2/2)

(1) Standard deviation: this is used to determine the dispersion of the data in its distribution with respect to the mean. The lower the value, the more clustered the data will be around the sample mean.

(2) C.V. = Coefficient of variation. Ratio between the standard deviation and the sample mean. In our case, we use it to estimate the degree of agreement between the answers of the different experts. The lower the value of the coefficient of variation, the greater the concordance in the answers.

Mean \geq 2: High affectation

1 \leq Mean < 2: Medium affectation

0 \leq Mean < 1: Low affectation

CLIMATIC AND OCEANIC-METEOROLOGICAL ELEMENTS

Air Temperature:
For the period 2011-2020, the average annual air temperature in Vilanova de Arousa was 15.1°C and there was an average of 40 warm days per year (maximum temperature above 25°C). By 2050, it is expected that the average air temperature will be 16.6°C, and that we will have an average of approximately 60 warm days per year.

Water surface temperature:
During the period 2011-2020, there was an average of 49 days/year with maximum water surface temperature above 20°C in the inner zone of the Ría de Arousa and 10 days/year in the outer zone. By 2050, an average of 59 days/year with maximum temperature above 20°C is expected in the inner zone of the estuary and 14 days/year in the outer zone.

Rainfall:
During the period 2011-2020, in the Ría de Arousa there were 6.2 days of extreme rainfall per year (above 33.8 litres/m² accumulated daily). For the period 2071-2100, 8.2 days of extreme rainfall are expected, although the increase will be concentrated in winter and decrease in summer.

Sea level:
During the period 1945-2015, sea level has risen by 20 cm, with a rate of increase of 2.4 cm/decade. By 2050, the average sea level will rise by 15-35 cm and by 2100 it will have risen by 0.5m to 1m. This is an average increase of 9.8 cm per decade from 2020.

Note: For every centimetre of sea level rise, 0.5 - 1 m of sand is lost.

Upwelling:
During the period 2011-2020, the average volume of water upwelling in the Ria de Arousa (upwelling index) during April-September (upwelling favourable semester) was 440 m³/s/km of coastline. By 2050, an average value of the upwelling index of 480 m³/s/km coastline is expected for the same semester (average increase of 11.25 m³/s/km coastline per decade).

Wind:
During the period 2011-2020 there was an average of 35 days/year with wind force 6 or higher (speed above 45 km/h) in the outer estuary area and an average of 1 day/year in the inner estuary area. By 2050, force 6 winds are expected to be present for 50 days/year in the outer zone. Winds of this intensity are not expected in the inner zone.

Acidification:
During the period 1980-2020 a decrease in pH/decade has been observed in the Ria de Arousa from 8.15 to 8.05 units in the outer zone, and from 8.10 to 7.95 units in the inner zone. In 2050 values of 7.95 (outer) and 7.85 (inner) are expected and by 2100 the pH is predicted to fall to 7.8 (outer) and 7.7 (inner), close to the threshold where it is corrosive to mussel shells and other bivalves (approx. 7.6 units).

STAGES IN THE MUSSEL PRODUCTION PROCESS									
Seed collection from collecting ropes	Seed collection from the rock	Seed tubing	Pre-fattening	Declumping and thinning	Fattening	Harvesting	Cleaning, declumping and grading	Register and transport to depuration	Depuration
1,17	1,87	1,35	1,00	1,39	1,04	1,17	0,70	0,74	0,48
2,26	2,30	1,30	1,96	1,57	2,09	1,61	0,52	0,39	0,70
1,35	1,65	1,26	1,57	1,35	1,48	1,13	0,48	0,39	0,57
0,70	1,78	0,61	0,61	0,57	0,48	0,48	0,22	0,17	0,22
1,00	1,09	0,65	0,91	0,70	0,91	0,52	0,26	0,13	0,22
1,30	1,57	1,48	1,09	1,30	1,17	1,26	0,43	0,26	0,17
2,52	2,52	2,00	2,35	2,00	2,17	1,91	0,70	0,61	0,65

Table 6. Mean matrix from Delphi 1

04 DELPHI 1: RISK SCENARIOS - RESULTS

Aggregated representation of climatic elements and process stages by level of impact.

Regarding climatic and ocean-meteorological elements, experts highlight the importance of Acidification and Water surface temperature.

Figure 14. Prioritization of the level of impact of climate and ocean-meteorological elements on a scale of 0 to 3.

Figure 15. Prioritization of the level of affection of phases of the mussel aquaculture process on a scale of 0 to 3.

The phase of Collecting the seed, both in the rock zone and on collecting ropes, is the one that accumulates the greatest number of risk scenarios.

04 DELPHI 1: RISK SCENARIOS - RESULTS

Detailed impact of climatic and oceanic-meteorological elements with the greatest impact

As it can be seen, the climatic and oceanic-meteorological elements with the greatest impact on the aquaculture process are **Acidification, Surface water temperature, Rainfall, Air temperature and Wind**. Among these elements, according to the experts' opinion, the one that seems to have the greatest impact on the aquaculture process is the **pH**, since if it drops to **7.7 within the estuary**, with 7.6 being the threshold, it will start to be **corrosive** to mussel shells and other bivalves.

Figure 16. Detailed impact of the five climatic and oceanic-meteorological elements with the greatest impact according to Mode.

04 DELPHI 1: RISK SCENARIOS - RESULTS

Detailed analysis of the impact on the most sensitive process stages

In the case of the process stages, those most influenced by climatic elements are (in order from most to least affected): Seed collection from the rock and from the ropes, Pre-fattening, Fattening and Seed tubing.

Figure 17. Detailed analysis of the impact on the five most sensitive process stages according to Mode.

04 DELPHI 1: RISK SCENARIOS - RESULTS

Ranking of the 13 highest-priority risk scenarios*, ordered by mean score

Scenario	Mean	Coefficient of variation	Scenario	Mean	Coefficient of variation	Scenario	Mean	Coefficient of variation
Acidification → Seed from ropes	2,52	0,26	Acidification → Fattening	2,17	0,38	Water surface temperature → Pre-fattening	1,96	0,36
Acidification → Seed from the rock	2,52	0,26	Water surface temperature → Fattening	2,09	0,41	Acidification → Harvesting	1,91	0,47
Acidification → Pre-fattening	2,35	0,33	Acidification → Seed tubing	2,00	0,45	Air temperature → Seed from the rock	1,87	0,46
Water surface temperature → Seed from the rock	2,30	0,28	Acidification → Declumping	2,00	0,43	Wind → Seed from the rock	1,57	0,46
Water surface temperature → Seed from ropes	2,26	0,33						

*Selection criteria:

To measure the level of impact, the average of the experts' responses has been used, taking 1.5 as the minimum threshold.

To assess consensus, the coefficient of variation was used, with a maximum threshold of 0.50.

04 DELPHI 1: RISK SCENARIOS - RESULTS

13 risk scenarios prioritized

This figure portrays the high importance in the production of the increase of **acidification**, present in 7 of the 13 prioritized scenarios.

This is followed by the impact of the increase in **ocean surface temperature**, which is present in 4 out of 13 scenarios prioritized.

In addition, regarding the stages of the production process, the experts identify the **collection of the mussel seed from the rock** as the most sensitive phase, as it is present in 4 of the 13 scenarios.

Figure 18. Relationship between the climatic and ocean-meteorological variables with the greatest impact and the stages of the process most affected

TransformAr

01 Introduction

02 Context and background

03 Delphi method

04 Delphi 1

05 Delphi 2

06 Assessment of adaptive capacity

07 RI final results

08 Priority lines of action

05 Delphi 2: Resilience GAPS

5.1 Expert panel distribution

5.2 Survey

5.4 Results

[General index](#)

Stakeholder groups	Experts
Science / Academia	4
Government	3
Society	4
Environment	4
Economy	5
	20

Gender	Total	%
Men	9	45,00%
Women	11	55,00%
	20	100%

As mentioned in Delphi 1 section, the objective of constructing a Resilience Index requires the identification of the **key players involved in the case study region**, specifically, those with knowledge and expertise about resilience, climate change and socioeconomic aspects of the Key Community System of the mussel aquaculture in Galicia. Hence, while this work does not strive to provide an exhaustive list, it aims to include a representative sample of the stakeholders relevant to the project.

According to the participant thresholds accepted for the Delphi method (7-30 experts), for Delphi 2 a total of **23 experts have been invited** (those who completed the Delphi 1), of which **20 have been engaged to complete their participation in all three rounds**. These 20 experts were distributed in a well-balanced proportion among the five stakeholder groups.

In terms of gender, we again observe a **distribution very close to full parity**.

Table 7. Expert panel distribution in Delphi 2

Members of the expert panel received an **e-mail invitation** to the online questionnaire including the **Delphi 1 results attached** in case some respondent needed extra information about the priority risk scenarios selected.

Minor deadline extensions in each round were necessary, therefore the final schedule followed for conducting the three rounds was as follows:

- Round 1: 26/09 – 09/10/2023
- Round 2: 10/10 – 20/10/2023
- Round 3: 23/10 – 30/10/2023

Following the Delphi method, after receiving the responses to the online questionnaire in each round, an **anonymized aggregation of the answers was carried out by statistical analysis and shared with the experts** prior to the start of the next round. The aim was to bring their **responses closer to consensus**, if they consider it opportune.

Figure 19. E-mail invitation to Delphi 2 – Round 1

The online questionnaire was also developed in the platform Medallia (formerly CheckMarket) and also in Spanish for a better understanding by local experts. The description of all the items in the form can be read in **English in pages 46-48**. In addition, all the results in this report are presented in English.

Esto es una encuesta previa y no se guardarán los resultados.

ÍNDICE DE RESILIENCIA OPERATIVA DEL CULTIVO DEL MEJILLÓN

Formulario Delphi 2 (Ronda 1)

Tras la consulta emitida el pasado mes de Julio para identificar los escenarios de riesgo prioritarios en el proceso de acuicultura del mejillón de la Ría de Arousa (Delphi 1), en esta segunda consulta (Delphi 2) se busca evaluar la eficacia de ciertos factores y herramientas para hacer frente a dichos escenarios de riesgo.

Como sabe, la metodología Delphi nos permitirá encontrar el consenso y llegar a conclusiones robustas tras el intercambio de resultados y el análisis de conocimientos y opiniones del panel de expertos/as del que forma parte, con más de 20 actores vinculados al sector mejillonero, al ámbito académico, a agentes sociales, a la administración y al medioambiente. Para ello, al igual que en el Delphi 1, se llevarán a cabo tres rondas de respuestas. Tras cada ronda recibirá los resultados globales y anonimizados de todos/as los/as expertos/as para la reconsideración de su respuestas de cara a la siguiente ronda.

Sólo necesitará unos minutos para completar este cuestionario y todas sus respuestas serán privadas y confidenciales.

El plazo para completar esta primera ronda finalizará el domingo 8 de octubre de 2023, a las 23:55 h (horario ampliado). Ante cualquier duda o aclaración que necesite, puede contactar con el equipo TransformAr-Galicia en el e-mail transformar@uvigo.gal o el teléfono 986 130 108.

Tras una extensa revisión de literatura científica y el intercambio con agentes del sector en los talleres llevados a cabo en Galicia en el seno del proyecto TransformAr, se han identificado 20 factores de resiliencia, clasificados en 5 dimensiones y con potencial para hacer frente a eventos adversos del cambio climático en el ámbito de la acuicultura del mejillón. A continuación, se mostrará una matriz por cada una de las cinco dimensiones. Cada matriz presentará cuatro factores de resiliencia en las filas y los escenarios de riesgo identificados por el panel de expertos en el Delphi 1 en las columnas.

DIMENSIÓN 1 DE 5: GOBERNANZA

* 1. Puntaje, empleando una escala entre 0 y 3, en qué medida contribuyen los siguientes factores de resiliencia relacionados con la **Gobernanza** (filas) a minimizar los impactos negativos provocados por cada uno de los siguientes escenarios de riesgo (columnas). Cada escenario de riesgo se define por el aumento de la variable climático-meteorológica indicada y una fase del proceso de acuicultura.

Si lo desea, puede añadir comentarios adicionales en la siguiente pregunta.

Siendo 0 = Sin contribución; 1 = Contribución baja; 2 = Contribución media; 3 = Contribución alta

Temperatura superficial del aire / Obtención de la zona de roca		Temperatura superficial del agua / Obtención de cuerdas de la zona de roca		Temperatura superficial del agua / Obtención de la zona de roca		Viento / Obtención de la zona de roca		Acidificación / Obtención de la zona de roca		Acidificación / Obtención de la zona de roca		Acidificación / Obtención de la zona de roca		Acidificación / Obtención de la zona de roca	

1.1 Programas de capacitación: Iniciativas conjuntas de formación dirigidas a autoridades reguladoras, sector productivo y otros agentes clave sobre los desafíos del cambio climático y cultura marítima que permitan dotarles de herramientas y conocimientos para implementar estrategias efectivas de adaptación

1.2 Gestión flexible: Empleo de principios de gestión adaptativa, tanto por parte de la administración pública como del sector productivo, para abordar la incertidumbre con un enfoque flexible y ágil (e.g. toma de decisiones iterativas, incorporación de retroalimentación constante y ajustes de supuestos según la evolución de los escenarios).

1.3 Planificación del espacio marino: Introducir en los Planes de Ordenación del Espacio Marítimo (POEM) estrategias que incorporen la evaluación de impactos potenciales del cambio climático en la acuicultura del mejillón y otras actividades marítimas, con el propósito de prevenir conflictos y promover una coexistencia sostenible entre diversos sectores.

1.4 Gestión de fondos público-privados: Evaluación de las necesidades financieras para la adaptación del sector con el propósito de crear y gestionar de forma eficiente fondos de origen público-privado que permitan llevar a cabo acciones preventivas y/o cubrir futuras contingencias.

2. Si lo desea, puede añadir cualquier comentario o aclaración que considere relevante sobre el contenido de la matriz que ha cubierto.

Le recordamos que en esta ocasión, como medida de flexibilidad, podrá pausar el cuestionario y continuarlo en otro momento. Para ello, tras cubrir alguna de las matrices del cuestionario, pulse en botón 'Siguiente' (para que se almacenen las respuestas) y después en el botón 'Pausa' de la página siguiente (ambos al final de cada página). Podrá retomar el cuestionario desde el botón 'Iniciar' del e-mail de invitación.

Siguiente »

Figure 20. Delphi 1 online questionnaire

RESULTS FROM DELPHI 2 ONLINE QUESTIONNAIRE

20 experts

260 resilience GAPS assessed

14 resilience factors prioritized

Following the completion of the third round of Delphi 2, the **average values of the expert panel scores have been multiplied by the averages assigned in Delphi 1 to the corresponding risk scenario.**

By doing this, we seek to calculate adjusted averages that help us to more objectively **assign the importance of the resilience factors identified**, considering the level of risk of the scenario we are assessing.

Therefore, in the next pages the following results are shown :

- In the **detailed matrixes of results per expert** "Risk Scenario Mean" and "Weighted Mean" are included. The former indicates the mean of the corresponding risk scenario, and the later indicates the weighted mean (Mean * Risk Scenario Mean).
- Below in this document, the **weighted mean** values are presented.

RESILIENCE GAPS - GOVERNANCE	Expert																				Mean	Mode	Median	Standard Dev. ⁽¹⁾	C.V. ⁽²⁾	Mean Risk Scenario	Weighted mean ⁽³⁾
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20							
1. Training programmes vs. Air temperature / Seed collection from the rock	2	1	1	0	1	1	2	1	2	2	1	1	2	1	1	0	3	2	2	1	1,35	1	1	0,75	0,55	1,87	2,52
2. Training programmes vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the ropes	2	1	1	0	1	1	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	3	2	2	1	1,50	2	2	0,69	0,46	2,26	3,39
3. Training programmes vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the rock	2	1	3	0	1	1	3	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	2	3	2	2	1	1,70	2	2	0,80	0,47	2,30	3,92
4. Training programmes vs. Water surface temperature / Pre-fattening	2	1	3	0	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	3	2	1	1	1,35	1	1	0,75	0,55	1,96	2,64
5. Training programmes vs. Water surface temperature / Fattening	2	1	3	0	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	3	2	1	1	1,35	1	1	0,75	0,55	2,09	2,82
6. Training programmes vs. Wind / Seed collection from the rock	2	1	0	0	1	2	2	1	0	0	1	1	2	1	1	0	3	2	0	1	1,05	1	1	0,89	0,84	1,57	1,64
7. Training programmes vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the ropes	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	2	3	2	1	1	1,45	1	1	0,60	0,42	2,52	3,66
8. Training programmes vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the rock	2	1	2	1	1	0	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	2	3	2	1	1	1,35	1	1	0,67	0,50	2,52	3,40
9. Training programmes vs. Acidification / Seed tubing	2	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	2	1	1	3	2	0	1	1,05	1	1	0,76	0,72	2,00	2,10
10. Training programmes vs. Acidification / Pre-fattening	2	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	2	1	1	1	3	2	0	1	1,00	1	1	0,79	0,79	2,35	2,35
11. Training programmes vs. Acidification / Declumping	2	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	2	1	1	1	3	2	0	1	1,00	1	1	0,79	0,79	2,00	2,00
12. Training programmes vs. Acidification / Fattening	2	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	2	1	1	0	3	2	0	1	0,95	1	1	0,83	0,87	2,17	2,07
13. Training programmes vs. Acidification / Harvesting	2	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	2	1	1	0	3	2	0	1	1,00	1	1	0,79	0,79	1,91	1,91
14. Flexible management vs. Air temperature / Seed collection from the rock	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	3	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	1	1,75	2	2	0,55	0,31	1,87	3,27
15. Flexible management vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the ropes	2	1	1	2	3	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	3	2	2	2	1	1,90	2	2	0,55	0,29	2,26	4,30
16. Flexible management vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the rock	2	1	2	2	3	2	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	1	2	3	2	2	2	1	2,00	2	2	0,56	0,28	2,30	4,61
17. Flexible management vs. Water surface temperature / Pre-fattening	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	1,85	2	2	0,37	0,20	1,96	3,62
18. Flexible management vs. Water surface temperature / Fattening	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	1	1,85	2	2	0,37	0,20	2,09	3,86
19. Flexible management vs. Wind / Seed collection from the rock	2	1	2	2	2	2	3	2	1	0	2	3	2	1	2	1	2	2	0	1	1,65	2	2	0,81	0,49	1,57	2,58
20. Flexible management vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the ropes	2	1	2	3	2	1	1	2	1	1	2	3	2	1	2	1	2	2	0	1	1,60	2	2	0,75	0,47	2,52	4,03
21. Flexible management vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the rock	2	1	2	3	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	3	2	1	2	2	2	2	0	1	1,70	2	2	0,73	0,43	2,52	4,29
22. Flexible management vs. Acidification / Seed tubing	2	1	2	3	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	2	0	1	1,50	2	2	0,69	0,46	2,00	3,00
23. Flexible management vs. Acidification / Pre-fattening	2	1	2	3	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	0	1	1,55	2	2	0,69	0,44	2,35	3,64
24. Flexible management vs. Acidification / Declumping	2	1	2	3	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	0	1	1,45	1	1	0,69	0,47	2,00	2,90
25. Flexible management vs. Acidification / Fattening	2	1	2	3	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	0	1	1,45	1	1	0,69	0,47	2,17	3,15
26. Flexible management vs. Acidification / Harvesting	2	1	2	3	2	2	0	2	1	0	2	3	2	1	1	0	2	2	0	1	1,45	2	2	0,94	0,65	1,91	2,77
27. Marine spatial planning vs. Air temperature / Seed collection from the rock	2	1	1	2	2	0	2	2	1	0	2	3	2	3	1	1	3	2	0	1	1,55	2	2	0,94	0,61	1,87	2,90
28. Marine spatial planning vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the ropes	2	1	1	2	2	0	3	3	2	0	2	2	2	3	2	2	3	1	0	1	1,70	2	2	0,98	0,58	2,26	3,84
29. Marine spatial planning vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the rock	2	1	1	2	2	1	3	2	2	0	2	3	2	3	2	2	3	2	0	1	1,80	2	2	0,89	0,50	2,30	4,15
30. Marine spatial planning vs. Water surface temperature / Pre-fattening	2	1	2	2	2	0	2	2	2	0	2	1	2	3	2	2	3	1	0	2	1,65	2	2	0,88	0,53	1,96	3,23
31. Marine spatial planning vs. Water surface temperature / Fattening	2	1	2	2	2	0	2	2	2	0	2	1	2	3	2	2	3	1	0	2	1,65	2	2	0,88	0,53	2,09	3,44
32. Marine spatial planning vs. Wind / Seed collection from the rock	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	0	2	3	2	3	2	2	3	2	0	1	1,80	2	2	0,83	0,46	1,57	2,82
33. Marine spatial planning vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the ropes	2	1	2	3	2	0	2	1	1	0	2	2	2	3	2	1	3	1	0	2	1,60	2	2	0,94	0,59	2,52	4,03
34. Marine spatial planning vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the rock	2	1	2	3	2	1	1	2	1	0	2	3	2	3	2	2	3	2	0	1	1,75	2	2	0,91	0,52	2,52	4,41
35. Marine spatial planning vs. Acidification / Seed tubing	2	1	2	2	2	0	1	1	1	0	2	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	0	2	1,45	2	2	0,89	0,61	2,00	2,90
36. Marine spatial planning vs. Acidification / Pre-fattening	2	1	2	2	2	0	1	1	1	0	2	1	2	3	1	2	3	1	0	2	1,45	2	2	0,89	0,61	2,35	3,40
37. Marine spatial planning vs. Acidification / Declumping	2	1	2	2	2	0	1	1	1	0	2	1	2	3	1	1	3	1	0	2	1,40	1	1	0,88	0,63	2,00	2,80
38. Marine spatial planning vs. Acidification / Fattening	2	1	0	2	2	0	1	1	1	0	2	1	2	3	1	1	3	1	0	2	1,30	1	1	0,92	0,71	2,17	2,83
39. Marine spatial planning vs. Acidification / Harvesting	2	1	0	2	2	0	0	1	1	0	2	1	2	3	1	0	3	1	0	2	1,20	2	1	1,01	0,84	1,91	2,30
40. Public-private fund management vs. Air temperature / Seed collection from the rock	0	2	2	2	1	2	3	1	2	2	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	2	2	0	1,55	2	2	0,76	0,49	1,87	2,90
41. Public-private fund management vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the ropes	0	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	0	1,70	2	2	0,73	0,43	2,26	3,84
42. Public-private fund management vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the rock	0	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	0	1,60	2	2	0,68	0,43	2,30	3,69
43. Public-private fund management vs. Water surface temperature / Pre-fattening	0	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	0	1,35	2	1	0,67	0,50	1,96	2,64
44. Public-private fund management vs. Water surface temperature / Fattening	0	2	2	2	1	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	2	0	1,40	2	2	0,68	0,49	2,09	2,92
45. Public-private fund management vs. Wind / Seed collection from the rock	0	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	0	0	1,35	2	2	0,75	0,55	1,57	2,11
46. Public-private fund management vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the ropes	0	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	1	2	2	0	0	1,20	1	1	0,70	0,58	2,52	3,03
47. Public-private fund management vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the rock	0	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	0	0	1,30	2	1	0,73	0,56	2,52	3,28
48. Public-private fund management vs. Acidification / Seed tubing	0	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	0	0	1,10	1	1	0,72	0,65	2,00	2,20
49. Public-private fund management vs. Acidification / Pre-fattening	0	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	0	0	1,05	1	1	0,69	0,65	2,35	2,47
50. Public-private fund management vs. Acidification / Declumping	0	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	0	0	1,05	1	1	0,69	0,65	2,00	2,10
51. Public-private fund management vs. Acidification / Fattening	0	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	0	0	1,05	1	1	0,69	0,65	2,17	2,28
52. Public-private fund management vs. Acidification / Harvesting	0	2	2	2	1	2	0	1	1	0	1	3	1	1	1	0	2	2	0	0	1,10	1	1	0,91	0,83	1,91	2,10

Table 8. Matrix of results by expert in the Governance dimension

- (1) Standard deviation: this is used to determine the dispersion of the data in its distribution with respect to the mean. The lower the value, the more grouped the data will be around the sample mean.
- (2) C.V. = Coefficient of variation. Ratio between the standard deviation and the sample mean. In our case we use it to estimate the degree of agreement between the answers of the different experts. The lower the value of the coefficient of variation, the greater the concordance in the answers.
- (3) Weighted mean: Result of multiplying the "Mean" by the "Mean Risk Score". It provides a weighted average according to the degree of risk of the scenario on which the performance of the corresponding resilience factor is being evaluated.

05 DELPHI 2: RESILIENCE GAPS - RESULTS

Matrix of results by expert. R&D&I dimension (2/5)

RESILIENCE GAPS - R+D+I	Expert																				Mean	Mode	Median	Standard Dev. ⁽¹⁾	C.V. ⁽²⁾	Mean Risk Scenario	Weighted mean (3)
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20							
53. Advanced scientific research vs. Air temperature / Seed collection from the rock	2	1	2	3	3	3	3	2	3	3	2	3	3	3	2	1	2	3	3	1	2,40	3	3	0,75	0,31	1,87	4,49
54. Advanced scientific research vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the ropes	2	1	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	2	3	3	3	3	2	3	3	3	1	2,65	3	3	0,67	0,25	2,26	5,99
55. Advanced scientific research vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the rock	2	1	2	3	3	3	3	2	3	3	2	3	3	3	3	3	2	3	3	1	2,55	3	3	0,69	0,27	2,30	5,88
56. Advanced scientific research vs. Water surface temperature / Pre-fattening	2	1	2	3	3	2	3	3	3	3	2	3	3	3	3	2	2	3	3	1	2,50	3	3	0,69	0,28	1,96	4,89
57. Advanced scientific research vs. Water surface temperature / Fattening	2	1	2	3	3	2	3	3	3	3	2	3	3	3	3	2	2	3	3	1	2,50	3	3	0,69	0,28	2,09	5,22
58. Advanced scientific research vs. Wind / Seed collection from the rock	2	1	1	3	3	3	3	2	3	2	2	3	3	3	2	1	2	3	2	1	2,25	3	2	0,79	0,35	1,57	3,52
59. Advanced scientific research vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the ropes	2	1	3	3	3	3	3	2	3	3	2	3	3	3	2	3	2	3	2	1	2,50	3	3	0,69	0,28	2,52	6,30
60. Advanced scientific research vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the rock	2	1	2	3	3	3	3	2	3	3	2	3	3	3	2	3	2	3	2	1	2,45	3	3	0,69	0,28	2,52	6,18
61. Advanced scientific research vs. Acidification / Seed tubing	2	1	3	3	3	1	0	2	2	2	2	2	3	3	2	3	2	3	2	2	2,15	2	2	0,81	0,38	2,00	4,30
62. Advanced scientific research vs. Acidification / Pre-fattening	2	1	3	3	3	1	0	2	2	2	2	2	3	3	2	2	2	3	2	2	2,10	2	2	0,79	0,38	2,35	4,93
63. Advanced scientific research vs. Acidification / Declumping	2	1	3	3	3	3	0	2	2	2	2	2	3	3	2	2	2	3	2	2	2,20	2	2	0,77	0,35	2,00	4,40
64. Advanced scientific research vs. Acidification / Fattening	2	1	3	3	3	1	0	2	2	2	2	2	3	3	2	1	2	3	2	2	2,05	2	2	0,83	0,40	2,17	4,46
65. Advanced scientific research vs. Acidification / Harvesting	2	1	0	3	3	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	3	3	2	1	2	3	2	2	1,95	2	2	0,89	0,45	1,91	3,73
66. Improving exposure forecasts vs. Air temperature / Seed collection from the rock	1	1	2	2	2	3	3	2	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	1	3	3	2	1	2,05	2	2	0,69	0,33	1,87	3,83
67. Improving exposure forecasts vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the ropes	1	1	2	2	2	3	3	2	3	3	2	2	2	3	2	3	3	3	2	1	2,25	2	2	0,72	0,32	2,26	5,09
68. Improving exposure forecasts vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the rock	1	1	2	2	2	3	3	2	3	3	2	2	2	3	2	3	3	3	2	1	2,25	2	2	0,72	0,32	2,30	5,18
69. Improving exposure forecasts vs. Water surface temperature / Pre-fattening	1	1	2	2	2	3	1	3	2	3	2	2	2	3	2	2	3	3	2	1	2,10	2	2	0,72	0,34	1,96	4,11
70. Improving exposure forecasts vs. Water surface temperature / Fattening	1	1	2	2	2	3	1	3	2	3	2	2	2	3	2	2	3	3	2	1	2,10	2	2	0,72	0,34	2,09	4,38
71. Improving exposure forecasts vs. Wind / Seed collection from the rock	1	1	2	2	2	3	3	2	2	1	2	2	2	3	2	1	3	3	2	1	2,05	2	2	0,76	0,37	1,57	3,21
72. Improving exposure forecasts vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the ropes	1	1	2	2	2	1	3	2	3	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	3	3	2	1	2,05	2	2	0,69	0,33	2,52	5,17
73. Improving exposure forecasts vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the rock	1	1	2	2	2	1	3	2	3	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	3	3	2	1	2,05	2	2	0,69	0,33	2,52	5,17
74. Improving exposure forecasts vs. Acidification / Seed tubing	1	1	2	2	2	1	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	3	2	2	1	1,80	2	2	0,70	0,39	2,00	3,60
75. Improving exposure forecasts vs. Acidification / Pre-fattening	1	1	2	2	2	1	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	1	3	2	2	1	1,75	2	2	0,72	0,41	2,35	4,11
76. Improving exposure forecasts vs. Acidification / Declumping	1	1	2	2	2	1	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	1	3	2	2	1	1,75	2	2	0,72	0,41	2,00	3,50
77. Improving exposure forecasts vs. Acidification / Fattening	1	1	2	2	2	1	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	1	3	2	2	1	1,75	2	2	0,72	0,41	2,17	3,80
78. Improving exposure forecasts vs. Acidification / Harvesting	1	1	2	2	2	1	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	0	3	3	2	1	1,70	2	2	0,86	0,51	1,91	3,25
79. Applied biotechnology projects vs. Air temperature / Seed collection from the rock	2	3	0	2	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	3	3	1	0	3	1	0	0	1,25	1	1	1,07	0,86	1,87	2,34
80. Applied biotechnology projects vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the ropes	2	3	0	3	1	2	3	2	2	0	1	2	3	3	2	2	3	3	0	1	1,90	2	2	1,07	0,56	2,26	4,30
81. Applied biotechnology projects vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the rock	2	3	0	3	1	2	1	2	2	0	1	1	3	3	2	2	3	1	0	0	1,60	2	2	1,10	0,68	2,30	3,69
82. Applied biotechnology projects vs. Water surface temperature / Pre-fattening	2	3	0	3	2	2	2	2	2	0	1	1	3	3	2	2	3	3	0	1	1,85	2	2	1,04	0,56	1,96	3,62
83. Applied biotechnology projects vs. Water surface temperature / Fattening	2	3	0	3	2	2	2	2	2	0	1	1	3	3	2	2	3	3	0	1	1,85	2	2	1,04	0,56	2,09	3,86
84. Applied biotechnology projects vs. Wind / Seed collection from the rock	2	3	0	2	1	2	2	1	2	0	1	1	3	3	1	0	3	1	0	0	1,40	1	1	1,10	0,78	1,57	2,19
85. Applied biotechnology projects vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the ropes	2	3	2	3	1	3	3	2	1	0	1	2	3	3	2	2	3	3	0	1	2,00	3	2	1,03	0,51	2,52	5,04
86. Applied biotechnology projects vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the rock	2	3	0	3	2	3	1	2	1	0	1	1	3	3	2	2	3	1	0	0	1,65	3	2	1,14	0,69	2,52	4,16
87. Applied biotechnology projects vs. Acidification / Seed tubing	2	3	2	3	2	2	0	2	1	0	1	2	3	3	2	2	3	3	0	1	1,85	2	2	1,04	0,56	2,00	3,70
88. Applied biotechnology projects vs. Acidification / Pre-fattening	2	3	2	3	2	3	0	2	1	0	1	1	3	3	2	2	3	3	0	1	1,85	3	2	1,09	0,59	2,35	4,34
89. Applied biotechnology projects vs. Acidification / Declumping	2	3	2	3	2	3	0	2	1	0	1	1	3	3	2	1	3	3	0	1	1,80	3	2	1,11	0,61	2,00	3,60
90. Applied biotechnology projects vs. Acidification / Fattening	2	3	2	3	2	3	0	2	1	0	1	1	3	3	2	1	3	3	0	1	1,80	3	2	1,11	0,61	2,17	3,91
91. Applied biotechnology projects vs. Acidification / Harvesting	2	3	2	3	2	1	0	2	1	0	1	1	3	3	2	0	3	3	0	1	1,65	3	2	1,14	0,69	1,91	3,16
92. Development of new technologies vs. Air temperature / Seed collection from the rock	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	0	3	3	3	2	1	2	2	0	1	1,60	2	2	0,82	0,51	1,87	2,99
93. Development of new technologies vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the ropes	1	1	2	2	2	2	3	3	3	2	1	2	3	3	2	2	2	2	0	2	2,00	2	2	0,79	0,40	2,26	4,52
94. Development of new technologies vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the rock	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	3	2	1	0	3	3	2	2	2	2	0	1	1,70	2	2	0,86	0,51	2,30	3,92
95. Development of new technologies vs. Water surface temperature / Pre-fattening	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	1	2	3	3	2	2	2	2	0	2	1,90	2	2	0,72	0,38	1,96	3,72
96. Development of new technologies vs. Water surface temperature / Fattening	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	1	2	3	3	2	2	2	2	0	2	1,90	2	2	0,72	0,38	2,09	3,97
97. Development of new technologies vs. Wind / Seed collection from the rock	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	0	3	3	3	2	1	2	2	0	1	1,60	2	2	0,82	0,51	1,57	2,50
98. Development of new technologies vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the ropes	1	1	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	1	2	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	0	2	1,90	2	2	0,72	0,38	2,52	4,79
99. Development of new technologies vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the rock	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	3	2	2	1	0	3	3	2	2	2	2	0	1	1,70	2	2	0,86	0,51	2,52	4,29
100. Development of new technologies vs. Acidification / Seed tubing	1	1	2	2	2	3	0	2	1	2	1	2	3	3	2	2	2	2	0	1	1,70	2	2	0,86	0,51	2,00	3,40
101. Development of new technologies vs. Acidification / Pre-fattening	1	1	2	2	2	3	0	2	1	2	1	0	3	3	2	2	2	2	0	1	1,60	2	2	0,94	0,59	2,35	3,76
102. Development of new technologies vs. Acidification / Declumping	1	1	2	2	2	3	0	2	1	2	1	2	3	3	2	1	2	2	0	1	1,65	2	2	0,88	0,53	2,00	3,30
103. Development of new technologies vs. Acidification / Fattening	1	1	2	2	2	3	0	2	1	2	1	0	3	3	2	1	2	2	0	1	1,55	2	2	0,94	0,61	2,17	3,37
104. Development of new technologies vs. Acidification / Harvesting	1	1	2	2	2	3	0	2	1	2	1	1	3	3	1	1	2	2	0	1	1,55	1	2	0,89	0,57	1,91	2,97

Table 9. Matrix of results by expert in the R&D&I dimension

- Standard deviation: this is used to determine the dispersion of the data in its distribution with respect to the mean. The lower the value, the more grouped the data will be around the sample mean.
- C.V. = Coefficient of variation. Ratio between the standard deviation and the sample mean. In our case we use it to estimate the degree of agreement between the answers of the different experts. The lower the value of the coefficient of variation, the greater the concordance in the answers.
- Weighted mean: Result of multiplying the "Mean" by the "Mean Risk Score". It provides a weighted average according to the degree of risk of the scenario on which the performance of the corresponding resilience factor is being evaluated.

05 DELPHI 2: RESILIENCE GAPS - RESULTS

Matrix of results by expert. RISK MANAGEMENT dimension (3/5)

RESILIENCE GAPS- RISK MANAGEMENT	Expert																				Mean	Mode	Median	Standard Dev. ⁽¹⁾	C.V. ⁽²⁾	Mean Risk Scenario	Weighted mean ⁽³⁾	
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20								
105. Multitrophic aquaculture vs. Air temperature / Seed collection from the rock	1	2	0	1	1	0	3	1	0	0	2	1	2	3	1	0	3	0	0	0	1,05	0	1	1,10	1,05	1,87	1,96	
106. Multitrophic aquaculture vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the ropes	1	2	0	1	2	0	2	1	1	0	2	3	2	3	1	1	3	2	0	0	1,35	1	1	1,04	0,77	2,26	3,05	
107. Multitrophic aquaculture vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the rock	1	2	0	1	1	0	3	1	1	0	2	1	2	3	1	1	3	0	0	0	1,15	1	1	1,04	0,90	2,30	2,65	
108. Multitrophic aquaculture vs. Water surface temperature / Pre-fattening	1	2	1	1	2	0	1	1	1	0	2	2	2	3	1	2	3	2	0	0	1,35	1	1	0,93	0,69	1,96	2,64	
109. Multitrophic aquaculture vs. Water surface temperature / Fattening	1	2	1	1	2	0	1	1	1	0	2	2	2	3	1	2	3	2	0	0	1,35	1	1	0,93	0,69	2,09	2,82	
110. Multitrophic aquaculture vs. Wind / Seed collection from the rock	1	2	0	1	1	0	3	1	0	0	2	1	2	3	1	0	3	0	0	0	1,05	0	1	1,10	1,05	1,57	1,64	
111. Multitrophic aquaculture vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the ropes	1	2	1	1	2	0	2	1	1	0	2	3	2	3	1	2	3	2	0	0	1,45	2	2	1,00	0,69	2,52	3,66	
112. Multitrophic aquaculture vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the rock	1	2	1	1	2	0	3	1	1	0	2	1	2	3	1	1	3	0	0	0	1,25	1	1	1,02	0,82	2,52	3,15	
113. Multitrophic aquaculture vs. Acidification / Seed tubing	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	0	0	2	2	2	3	1	2	3	2	0	0	1,35	1	1	0,93	0,69	2,00	2,70	
114. Multitrophic aquaculture vs. Acidification / Pre-fattening	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	0	0	2	3	2	3	1	2	3	2	0	0	1,40	1	1	0,99	0,71	2,35	3,29	
115. Multitrophic aquaculture vs. Acidification / Declumping	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	0	0	2	2	2	3	1	1	3	2	0	0	1,30	1	1	0,92	0,71	2,00	2,60	
116. Multitrophic aquaculture vs. Acidification / Fattening	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	0	0	2	3	2	3	1	1	3	2	0	0	1,35	1	1	0,99	0,73	2,17	2,93	
117. Multitrophic aquaculture vs. Acidification / Harvesting	1	2	1	1	2	1	1	1	0	0	2	3	2	3	1	0	3	2	0	0	1,30	1	1	1,03	0,79	1,91	2,49	
118. Tailored insurance cover vs. Air temperature / Seed collection from the rock	0	1	0	2	1	0	3	2	1	1	0	2	1	1	1	0	2	1	1	0	1,00	1	1	0,86	0,86	1,87	1,87	
119. Tailored insurance cover vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the ropes	0	1	0	2	1	0	0	2	2	1	0	2	1	1	1	2	2	1	1	1	1,05	1	1	0,76	0,72	2,26	3,05	
120. Tailored insurance cover vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the rock	0	1	0	2	1	0	0	1	2	1	0	2	1	1	1	2	2	1	1	0	0,95	1	1	0,76	0,80	2,30	2,19	
121. Tailored insurance cover vs. Water surface temperature / Pre-fattening	0	1	0	2	1	2	0	1	2	1	0	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	2	1	1,10	1	1	0,72	0,65	1,96	2,15	
122. Tailored insurance cover vs. Water surface temperature / Fattening	0	1	0	2	1	2	0	1	2	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	1	1,05	1	1	0,69	0,65	2,09	2,19	
123. Tailored insurance cover vs. Wind / Seed collection from the rock	0	1	0	2	1	2	3	1	3	0	0	2	1	1	1	0	2	1	0	0	1,05	0	1	1,00	0,95	1,57	1,64	
124. Tailored insurance cover vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the ropes	0	1	0	2	1	2	0	2	1	1	0	2	1	1	1	2	2	1	0	1	1,05	1	1	0,76	0,72	2,52	2,65	
125. Tailored insurance cover vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the rock	0	1	0	2	1	2	3	2	1	1	0	2	1	1	1	1	2	1	0	0	1,10	1	1	0,85	0,77	2,52	2,77	
126. Tailored insurance cover vs. Acidification / Seed tubing	0	1	0	2	1	2	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	0,95	1	1	0,60	0,64	2,00	1,90	
127. Tailored insurance cover vs. Acidification / Pre-fattening	0	1	0	2	1	2	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	1	1	0,95	1	1	0,60	0,64	2,35	2,23	
128. Tailored insurance cover vs. Acidification / Declumping	0	1	0	2	1	2	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	2	1	1	1	0,90	1	1	0,64	0,71	2,00	1,80	
129. Tailored insurance cover vs. Acidification / Fattening	0	1	0	2	1	2	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	2	1	1	1	0,90	1	1	0,64	0,71	2,17	1,96	
130. Tailored insurance cover vs. Acidification / Harvesting	0	1	0	2	1	3	1	1	0	1	0	3	1	1	1	0	2	1	1	1	1,05	1	1	0,89	0,84	1,91	2,01	
131. Ecosystem Approaches to Aquaculture (EEA) vs. Air temperature / Seed collection from the rock	3	2	2	2	3	0	1	2	2	2	3	2	2	2	2	0	3	2	2	0	1,85	2	2	0,93	0,50	1,87	3,46	
132. Ecosystem Approaches to Aquaculture (EEA) vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the ropes	3	2	2	2	3	2	3	2	2	2	3	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	0	2,15	2	2	0,67	0,31	2,26	4,86	
133. Ecosystem Approaches to Aquaculture (EEA) vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the rock	3	2	2	2	3	2	1	2	2	2	3	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	0	2,05	2	2	0,69	0,33	2,30	4,72	
134. Ecosystem Approaches to Aquaculture (EEA) vs. Water surface temperature / Pre-fattening	3	2	2	2	3	2	3	2	2	2	3	1	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	0	2,10	2	2	0,72	0,34	1,96	4,11	
135. Ecosystem Approaches to Aquaculture (EEA) vs. Water surface temperature / Fattening	3	2	2	2	3	2	3	2	2	2	3	1	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	0	2,10	2	2	0,72	0,34	2,09	4,38	
136. Ecosystem Approaches to Aquaculture (EEA) vs. Wind / Seed collection from the rock	3	2	2	2	3	2	1	2	2	1	3	2	2	2	2	1	3	2	2	0	1,95	2	2	0,76	0,39	1,57	3,05	
137. Ecosystem Approaches to Aquaculture (EEA) vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the ropes	3	2	2	2	3	2	3	2	2	2	3	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	0	2,15	2	2	0,67	0,31	2,52	5,42	
138. Ecosystem Approaches to Aquaculture (EEA) vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the rock	3	2	2	2	3	2	1	2	2	2	3	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	0	2,05	2	2	0,69	0,33	2,52	5,17	
139. Ecosystem Approaches to Aquaculture (EEA) vs. Acidification / Seed tubing	3	2	2	1	3	2	1	2	2	2	3	1	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	0	1,95	2	2	0,76	0,39	2,00	3,90	
140. Ecosystem Approaches to Aquaculture (EEA) vs. Acidification / Pre-fattening	3	2	2	1	3	2	1	2	2	2	3	1	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	0	1,95	2	2	0,76	0,39	2,35	4,58	
141. Ecosystem Approaches to Aquaculture (EEA) vs. Acidification / Declumping	3	2	2	1	3	2	1	2	2	2	3	1	2	2	2	1	3	2	2	0	1,90	2	2	0,79	0,41	2,00	3,80	
142. Ecosystem Approaches to Aquaculture (EEA) vs. Acidification / Fattening	3	2	2	1	3	2	1	2	2	2	3	1	2	2	2	1	3	2	2	0	1,90	2	2	0,79	0,41	2,17	4,13	
143. Ecosystem Approaches to Aquaculture (EEA) vs. Acidification / Harvesting	3	2	2	1	3	3	1	2	2	2	3	2	2	2	2	0	3	2	2	0	1,95	2	2	0,89	0,45	1,91	3,73	
144. Emergency action plans vs. Air temperature / Seed collection from the rock	1	1	3	3	2	3	2	3	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	3	2	0	1,90	2	2	0,79	0,41	1,87	3,55	
145. Emergency action plans vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the ropes	1	1	3	3	2	3	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	3	2	1	0	2,05	2	2	0,69	0,33	2,26	4,63	
146. Emergency action plans vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the rock	1	1	3	3	2	3	3	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	3	2	3	2	0	2,05	2	2	0,83	0,40	2,30	4,72	
147. Emergency action plans vs. Water surface temperature / Pre-fattening	1	1	3	3	2	3	3	2	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	3	2	1	2,00	2	2	0,73	0,36	1,96	3,91	
148. Emergency action plans vs. Water surface temperature / Fattening	1	1	3	3	2	3	3	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	3	2	1	2,00	2	2	0,73	0,36	2,09	4,17	
149. Emergency action plans vs. Wind / Seed collection from the rock	1	1	3	3	2	3	3	2	3	1	2	2	2	1	2	1	2	3	2	0	1,95	2	2	0,89	0,45	1,57	3,05	
150. Emergency action plans vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the ropes	1	1	3	3	2	3	3	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	3	2	1	2,05	2	2	0,69	0,33	2,52	5,17	
151. Emergency action plans vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the rock	1	1	3	3	2	3	3	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	3	2	0	2,00	2	2	0,79	0,40	2,52	5,04	
152. Emergency action plans vs. Acidification / Seed tubing	1	1	3	3	2	3	1	2	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	2	3	2	1	1,85	2	2	0,75	0,40	2,00	3,70
153. Emergency action plans vs. Acidification / Pre-fattening	1	1	3	3	2	3	1	2	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	2	2	3	2	1	1,85	2	2	0,75	0,40	2,35	4,34	
154. Emergency action plans vs. Acidification / Declumping	1	1	3	3	2	3	1	2	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	3	2	1	1,80	1	2	0,77	0,43	2,00	3,60	
155. Emergency action plans vs. Acidification / Fattening	1	1	3	3	2	3	1	2	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	1	2	3	2	1	1,80	1	2	0,77	0,43	2,17	3,91	
156. Emergency action plans vs. Acidification / Harvesting	1	1	3	3	2	3	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	2	0	2	3	2	1	1,80	2	2	0,83	0,46	1,91	3,44	

Table 10. Matrix of results by expert in the Risk Management dimension

- Standard deviation: this is used to determine the dispersion of the data in its distribution with respect to the mean. The lower the value, the more grouped the data will be around the sample mean.
- C.V. = Coefficient of variation. Ratio between the standard deviation and the sample mean. In our case we use it to estimate the degree of agreement between the answers of the different experts. The lower the value of the coefficient of variation, the greater the concordance in the answers.
- Weighted mean: Result of multiplying the "Mean" by the "Mean Risk Score". It provides a weighted average according to the degree of risk of the scenario on which the performance of the corresponding resilience factor is being evaluated.

05 DELPHI 2: RESILIENCE GAPS - RESULTS

Matrix of results by expert. COLLABORATION dimension (4/5)

RESILIENCE GAPS - COLLABORATION	Expert																				Mean	Mode	Median	Standard Dev. ⁽¹⁾	C.V. ⁽²⁾	Mean Risk Scenario	Weighted mean ⁽³⁾
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20							
157. Cross-sectoral collaboration vs. Air temperature / Seed collection from the rock	2	1	2	3	3	0	3	1	3	3	3	1	2	2	2	1	3	2	3	1	2,05	3	2	0,94	0,46	1,87	3,83
158. Cross-sectoral collaboration vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the ropes	1	1	2	3	3	1	2	2	3	3	3	1	2	2	2	2	3	2	3	1	2,10	2	2	0,79	0,38	2,26	4,75
159. Cross-sectoral collaboration vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the rock	2	1	2	3	3	2	3	2	3	3	3	1	2	2	2	2	3	2	3	1	2,25	2	2	0,72	0,32	2,30	5,18
160. Cross-sectoral collaboration vs. Water surface temperature / Pre-fattening	1	1	2	3	3	0	2	1	2	1	3	1	2	2	1	1	3	2	1	1	1,65	1	2	0,88	0,53	1,96	3,23
161. Cross-sectoral collaboration vs. Water surface temperature / Fattening	1	1	2	3	2	0	2	1	2	1	3	1	2	2	1	1	3	2	1	1	1,60	1	2	0,82	0,51	2,09	3,34
162. Cross-sectoral collaboration vs. Wind / Seed collection from the rock	1	1	1	3	3	2	3	2	3	1	3	1	2	2	2	0	3	2	3	1	1,95	3	2	0,94	0,48	1,57	3,05
163. Cross-sectoral collaboration vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the ropes	1	1	1	3	2	1	2	1	2	3	3	1	2	2	2	2	3	2	1	1	1,80	1	2	0,77	0,43	2,52	4,54
164. Cross-sectoral collaboration vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the rock	2	1	1	3	3	2	3	1	2	3	3	1	2	2	2	2	3	2	1	1	2,00	2	2	0,79	0,40	2,52	5,04
165. Cross-sectoral collaboration vs. Acidification / Seed tubing	1	1	1	1	2	1	0	1	1	1	3	1	2	2	1	2	3	2	1	1	1,40	1	1	0,75	0,54	2,00	2,80
166. Cross-sectoral collaboration vs. Acidification / Pre-fattening	1	1	1	1	2	1	0	1	1	1	3	1	2	2	1	1	3	2	1	1	1,35	1	1	0,75	0,55	2,35	3,17
167. Cross-sectoral collaboration vs. Acidification / Declumping	1	1	1	1	2	1	0	1	1	1	3	1	2	2	1	1	3	2	1	1	1,35	1	1	0,75	0,55	2,00	2,70
168. Cross-sectoral collaboration vs. Acidification / Fattening	1	1	1	1	2	1	0	1	1	1	3	1	2	2	1	1	3	2	1	1	1,35	1	1	0,75	0,55	2,17	2,93
169. Cross-sectoral collaboration vs. Acidification / Harvesting	1	1	2	1	2	1	0	1	1	1	3	2	2	2	1	0	3	2	1	1	1,40	1	1	0,82	0,59	1,91	2,68
170. Interdisciplinary cooperation vs. Air temperature / Seed collection from the rock	2	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	3	2	1	3	3	2	1	2,30	2	2	0,66	0,29	1,87	4,30
171. Interdisciplinary cooperation vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the ropes	2	3	3	3	3	2	3	3	2	2	3	2	2	3	2	3	3	3	2	1	2,50	3	3	0,61	0,24	2,26	5,65
172. Interdisciplinary cooperation vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the rock	2	3	3	3	3	2	2	3	2	2	3	2	2	3	2	3	3	3	2	1	2,45	3	3	0,60	0,25	2,30	5,65
173. Interdisciplinary cooperation vs. Water surface temperature / Pre-fattening	2	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	3	2	2	3	3	2	1	2,35	2	2	0,59	0,25	1,96	4,60
174. Interdisciplinary cooperation vs. Water surface temperature / Fattening	2	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	3	2	2	3	3	2	1	2,35	2	2	0,59	0,25	2,09	4,90
175. Interdisciplinary cooperation vs. Wind / Seed collection from the rock	2	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	3	2	1	3	3	2	1	2,30	2	2	0,66	0,29	1,57	3,60
176. Interdisciplinary cooperation vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the ropes	2	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	3	2	2	3	3	2	1	2,35	2	2	0,59	0,25	2,52	5,93
177. Interdisciplinary cooperation vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the rock	2	3	3	3	3	2	2	3	2	2	3	2	2	3	2	2	3	3	2	1	2,40	2	2	0,60	0,25	2,52	6,05
178. Interdisciplinary cooperation vs. Acidification / Seed tubing	2	3	3	3	3	2	0	2	2	2	3	1	2	2	2	3	3	3	2	1	2,20	2	2	0,83	0,38	2,00	4,40
179. Interdisciplinary cooperation vs. Acidification / Pre-fattening	2	3	3	3	3	2	0	2	2	2	3	1	2	3	2	2	3	3	2	1	2,20	2	2	0,83	0,38	2,35	5,17
180. Interdisciplinary cooperation vs. Acidification / Declumping	2	3	3	3	3	2	0	2	2	2	3	1	2	3	2	1	3	3	2	1	2,15	2	2	0,88	0,41	2,00	4,30
181. Interdisciplinary cooperation vs. Acidification / Fattening	2	3	3	3	3	2	0	2	2	2	3	1	2	3	2	1	3	3	2	1	2,15	2	2	0,88	0,41	2,17	4,67
182. Interdisciplinary cooperation vs. Acidification / Harvesting	2	3	3	3	3	2	0	2	2	2	3	1	2	3	2	1	3	3	2	1	2,15	2	2	0,88	0,41	1,91	4,11
183. International cooperation networks vs. Air temperature / Seed collection from the rock	1	1	1	3	3	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	0	2	3	2	1	1,65	1	2	0,81	0,49	1,87	3,08
184. International cooperation networks vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the ropes	1	1	1	3	3	2	2	3	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	3	2	2	1,90	2	2	0,72	0,38	2,26	4,30
185. International cooperation networks vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the rock	1	1	1	0	3	2	2	3	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	3	2	1	1,70	2	2	0,80	0,47	2,30	3,92
186. International cooperation networks vs. Water surface temperature / Pre-fattening	1	1	1	0	3	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	3	2	2	1,70	2	2	0,73	0,43	1,96	3,33
187. International cooperation networks vs. Water surface temperature / Fattening	1	1	1	0	3	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	3	2	2	1,70	2	2	0,73	0,43	2,09	3,55
188. International cooperation networks vs. Wind / Seed collection from the rock	1	1	1	0	3	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	1	2	3	2	1	1,60	2	2	0,75	0,47	1,57	2,50
189. International cooperation networks vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the ropes	1	1	1	0	3	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	1	2	3	2	2	1,65	2	2	0,75	0,45	2,52	4,16
190. International cooperation networks vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the rock	1	1	1	0	3	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	3	2	1	1,65	2	2	0,75	0,45	2,52	4,16
191. International cooperation networks vs. Acidification / Seed tubing	1	1	1	0	3	2	0	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	3	2	2	1,60	2	2	0,82	0,51	2,00	3,20
192. International cooperation networks vs. Acidification / Pre-fattening	1	1	1	0	3	2	0	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	1	2	3	2	2	1,55	2	2	0,83	0,53	2,35	3,64
193. International cooperation networks vs. Acidification / Declumping	1	1	1	0	3	2	0	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	1	2	3	2	2	1,55	2	2	0,83	0,53	2,00	3,10
194. International cooperation networks vs. Acidification / Fattening	1	1	1	0	3	2	0	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	1	2	3	2	2	1,55	2	2	0,83	0,53	2,17	3,37
195. International cooperation networks vs. Acidification / Harvesting	1	1	1	0	3	2	0	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	2	0	2	3	2	2	1,50	2	2	0,89	0,59	1,91	2,87
196. Intra-sectoral collaboration vs. Air temperature / Seed collection from the rock	2	2	0	0	2	1	2	1	1	0	1	1	2	2	1	0	2	2	0	1	1,15	2	1	0,81	0,71	1,87	2,15
197. Intra-sectoral collaboration vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the ropes	2	2	0	0	2	2	3	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	1,70	2	2	0,73	0,43	2,26	3,84
198. Intra-sectoral collaboration vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the rock	2	2	0	0	2	2	3	2	1	0	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	1	1,45	2	2	0,89	0,61	2,30	3,34
199. Intra-sectoral collaboration vs. Water surface temperature / Pre-fattening	2	2	0	0	2	2	3	1	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	1	1	1,55	2	2	0,76	0,49	1,96	3,03
200. Intra-sectoral collaboration vs. Water surface temperature / Fattening	2	2	0	0	2	2	3	1	2	1	1	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	1,55	2	2	0,76	0,49	2,09	3,23
201. Intra-sectoral collaboration vs. Wind / Seed collection from the rock	2	2	0	0	2	1	3	1	1	0	1	1	2	2	1	1	2	2	0	1	1,25	1	1	0,85	0,68	1,57	1,96
202. Intra-sectoral collaboration vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the ropes	2	2	0	0	2	1	2	2	1	1	1	1	2	2	2	1	2	2	2	1	1,45	2	2	0,69	0,47	2,52	3,66
203. Intra-sectoral collaboration vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the rock	2	2	0	0	2	1	3	1	1	0	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	1	1,35	2	2	0,88	0,65	2,52	3,40
204. Intra-sectoral collaboration vs. Acidification / Seed tubing	2	2	0	0	2	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	2	2	2	2	1	1,30	2	1	0,73	0,56	2,00	2,60
205. Intra-sectoral collaboration vs. Acidification / Pre-fattening	2	2	0	0	2	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	1	1,25	1	1	0,72	0,57	2,35	2,93
206. Intra-sectoral collaboration vs. Acidification / Declumping	2	2	0	0	2	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	1	2	2	0	1	1,15	1	1	0,75	0,65	2,00	2,30
207. Intra-sectoral collaboration vs. Acidification / Fattening	2	2	0	0	2	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	1	1,25	1	1	0,72	0,57	2,17	2,72
208. Intra-sectoral collaboration vs. Acidification / Harvesting	2	2	0	0	2	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	2	2	1	0	2	2	0	1	1,10	1	1	0,79	0,72	1,91	2,10

Table 11. Matrix of results by expert in the Collaboration dimension

- Standard deviation: this is used to determine the dispersion of the data in its distribution with respect to the mean. The lower the value, the more grouped the data will be around the sample mean.
- C.V. = Coefficient of variation. Ratio between the standard deviation and the sample mean. In our case we use it to estimate the degree of agreement between the answers of the different experts. The lower the value of the coefficient of variation, the greater the concordance in the answers.
- Weighted mean: Result of multiplying the "Mean" by the "Mean Risk Score". It provides a weighted average according to the degree of risk of the scenario on which the performance of the corresponding resilience factor is being evaluated.

05 DELPHI 2: RESILIENCE GAPS - RESULTS

Matrix of results by expert. OPERATIONAL ENVIRONMENT dimension (5/5)

RESILIENCE GAPS - OPERATIONAL ENVIRONMENT	Expert																				Mean	Mode	Median	Standard Dev. ⁽¹⁾	C.V. ⁽²⁾	Mean Risk Scenario	Weighted mean ⁽³⁾
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20							
209. Adaptation of infrastructures vs. Air temperature / Seed collection from the rock	2	2	3	3	1	0	3	1	1	1	2	0	2	2	2	0	2	2	0	1	1,50	2	2	1,00	0,67	1,87	2,80
210. Adaptation of infrastructures vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the ropes	2	2	1	3	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	1	1,75	2	2	0,64	0,36	2,26	3,96
211. Adaptation of infrastructures vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the rock	2	2	3	3	1	1	3	2	1	1	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	1	1,70	2	2	0,86	0,51	2,30	3,92
212. Adaptation of infrastructures vs. Water surface temperature / Pre-fattening	2	2	2	3	2	2	2	1	2	0	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	1	1,70	2	2	0,73	0,43	1,96	3,33
213. Adaptation of infrastructures vs. Water surface temperature / Fattening	2	2	2	3	2	2	2	1	2	0	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	1	1,70	2	2	0,73	0,43	2,09	3,55
214. Adaptation of infrastructures vs. Wind / Seed collection from the rock	2	2	3	3	1	2	3	2	1	0	2	0	2	2	2	1	2	2	0	1	1,65	2	2	0,93	0,57	1,57	2,58
215. Adaptation of infrastructures vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the ropes	2	2	2	3	2	1	2	2	1	0	2	1	0	2	2	2	2	2	0	1	1,70	2	2	0,73	0,43	2,52	4,29
216. Adaptation of infrastructures vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the rock	2	2	3	3	1	1	3	2	1	0	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	1	1,70	2	2	0,86	0,51	2,52	4,29
217. Adaptation of infrastructures vs. Acidification / Seed tubing	2	2	1	3	2	1	0	1	0	0	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	2	0	1	1,40	2	2	0,88	0,63	2,00	2,80
218. Adaptation of infrastructures vs. Acidification / Pre-fattening	2	2	1	3	2	1	0	1	0	0	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	0	1	1,35	2	2	0,88	0,65	2,35	3,17
219. Adaptation of infrastructures vs. Acidification / Declumping	2	2	1	3	2	1	0	1	0	0	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	0	1	1,35	2	2	0,88	0,65	2,00	2,70
220. Adaptation of infrastructures vs. Acidification / Fattening	2	2	1	3	2	1	0	1	0	0	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	0	1	1,35	2	2	0,88	0,65	2,17	2,93
221. Adaptation of infrastructures vs. Acidification / Harvesting	2	2	1	3	2	1	0	1	0	0	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	0	1	1,35	2	2	0,88	0,65	1,91	2,58
222. Monitoring and warning systems vs. Air temperature / Seed collection from the rock	2	1	2	3	2	1	2	3	3	3	2	2	1	2	2	2	3	3	2	2	2,15	2	2	0,67	0,31	1,87	4,02
223. Monitoring and warning systems vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the ropes	2	1	2	3	2	1	3	3	3	3	2	2	1	2	2	3	3	3	2	2	2,25	2	2	0,72	0,32	2,26	5,09
224. Monitoring and warning systems vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the rock	2	1	2	3	2	2	2	3	3	3	2	2	1	2	2	3	3	3	2	2	2,25	2	2	0,64	0,28	2,30	5,18
225. Monitoring and warning systems vs. Water surface temperature / Pre-fattening	2	1	2	3	3	1	2	3	3	3	2	2	1	2	2	2	3	3	2	2	2,20	2	2	0,70	0,32	1,96	4,30
226. Monitoring and warning systems vs. Water surface temperature / Fattening	2	1	2	3	3	1	3	3	3	3	2	2	1	2	2	2	3	3	2	2	2,25	2	2	0,72	0,32	2,09	4,70
227. Monitoring and warning systems vs. Wind / Seed collection from the rock	2	1	2	3	2	3	2	3	3	3	2	2	1	2	2	2	3	3	2	2	2,25	2	2	0,64	0,28	1,57	3,52
228. Monitoring and warning systems vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the ropes	2	1	2	3	2	1	2	3	3	3	2	2	1	2	2	3	3	3	2	2	2,20	2	2	0,70	0,32	2,52	5,55
229. Monitoring and warning systems vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the rock	2	1	2	2	2	2	2	3	3	3	2	2	1	2	2	2	3	3	2	2	2,15	2	2	0,59	0,27	2,52	5,42
230. Monitoring and warning systems vs. Acidification / Seed tubing	2	1	2	2	2	1	0	2	3	3	2	2	1	2	2	2	3	3	2	2	1,95	2	2	0,76	0,39	2,00	3,90
231. Monitoring and warning systems vs. Acidification / Pre-fattening	2	1	2	2	2	1	0	2	3	3	2	2	1	2	2	2	3	3	2	2	1,95	2	2	0,76	0,39	2,35	4,58
232. Monitoring and warning systems vs. Acidification / Declumping	2	1	2	2	2	1	0	2	3	3	2	2	1	2	2	2	3	3	2	2	1,95	2	2	0,76	0,39	2,00	3,90
233. Monitoring and warning systems vs. Acidification / Fattening	2	1	2	2	2	2	0	2	3	3	2	2	1	2	2	2	3	3	2	2	2,00	2	2	0,73	0,36	2,17	4,35
234. Monitoring and warning systems vs. Acidification / Harvesting	2	1	2	2	2	2	0	3	3	3	2	2	1	2	2	1	3	3	2	2	2,00	2	2	0,79	0,40	1,91	3,83
235. Improvement of production techniques vs. Air temperature / Seed collection from the rock	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	3	2	2	1	3	3	2	2	1,95	2	2	0,60	0,31	1,87	3,65
236. Improvement of production techniques vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the ropes	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	3	3	2	2	2	3	3	2	2	2,25	2	2	0,44	0,20	2,26	5,09
237. Improvement of production techniques vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the rock	2	2	2	2	2	2	1	2	3	2	2	1	3	2	2	2	3	3	2	2	2,10	2	2	0,55	0,26	2,30	4,84
238. Improvement of production techniques vs. Water surface temperature / Pre-fattening	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	1	3	2	2	2	3	3	2	2	2,15	2	2	0,49	0,23	1,96	4,21
239. Improvement of production techniques vs. Water surface temperature / Fattening	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	1	3	2	2	2	3	3	2	2	2,15	2	2	0,49	0,23	2,09	4,49
240. Improvement of production techniques vs. Wind / Seed collection from the rock	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	3	2	2	1	3	3	2	2	1,95	2	2	0,60	0,31	1,57	3,05
241. Improvement of production techniques vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the ropes	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	3	3	2	2	2	3	3	2	2	2,20	2	2	0,41	0,19	2,52	5,55
242. Improvement of production techniques vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the rock	2	2	2	3	2	1	1	2	2	2	2	1	3	2	2	2	3	3	2	2	2,05	2	2	0,60	0,30	2,52	5,17
243. Improvement of production techniques vs. Acidification / Seed tubing	2	2	2	3	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	3	3	2	2	2	3	3	2	3	2,20	2	2	0,70	0,32	2,00	4,40
244. Improvement of production techniques vs. Acidification / Pre-fattening	2	2	2	3	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	1	3	2	2	2	3	3	2	3	2,10	2	2	0,72	0,34	2,35	4,93
245. Improvement of production techniques vs. Acidification / Declumping	2	2	2	3	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	1	3	3	2	3	2,10	2	2	0,72	0,34	2,00	4,20
246. Improvement of production techniques vs. Acidification / Fattening	2	2	2	3	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	1	3	2	2	1	3	3	2	3	2,05	2	2	0,76	0,37	2,17	4,46
247. Improvement of production techniques vs. Acidification / Harvesting	2	2	2	3	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	2	3	2	2	1	3	3	2	3	2,10	2	2	0,72	0,34	1,91	4,02
248. Flexible procedures vs. Air temperature / Seed collection from the rock	2	3	2	3	2	2	2	2	3	3	2	2	3	3	2	1	3	3	3	1	2,35	2	2	0,67	0,29	1,87	4,39
249. Flexible procedures vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the ropes	2	3	2	3	2	2	2	2	3	3	2	2	3	3	2	3	3	3	3	2	2,50	2	3	0,51	0,21	2,26	5,65
250. Flexible procedures vs. Water surface temperature / Seed collection from the rock	2	3	2	3	2	1	2	2	3	3	2	2	3	3	2	3	3	3	3	1	2,40	3	3	0,68	0,28	2,30	5,53
251. Flexible procedures vs. Water surface temperature / Pre-fattening	2	3	2	3	2	2	2	2	3	3	2	2	3	3	2	2	3	3	3	2	2,45	2	2	0,51	0,21	1,96	4,79
252. Flexible procedures vs. Water surface temperature / Fattening	2	3	2	3	2	2	2	2	3	3	2	2	3	3	2	2	3	3	3	2	2,45	2	2	0,51	0,21	2,09	5,11
253. Flexible procedures vs. Wind / Seed collection from the rock	2	3	2	3	2	2	2	2	3	3	2	2	3	3	2	1	3	3	3	1	2,35	2	2	0,67	0,29	1,57	3,68
254. Flexible procedures vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the ropes	2	3	2	3	2	2	2	2	3	3	2	2	3	3	2	2	3	3	3	2	2,45	2	2	0,51	0,21	2,52	6,18
255. Flexible procedures vs. Acidification / Seed collection from the rock	2	3	2	3	2	1	2	2	3	3	2	2	3	3	2	2	3	3	3	1	2,35	2	2	0,67	0,29	2,52	5,93
256. Flexible procedures vs. Acidification / Seed tubing	2	3	2	3	2	2	0	2	2	3	2	1	3	3	2	1	3	3	3	2	2,20	2	2	0,83	0,38	2,00	4,40
257. Flexible procedures vs. Acidification / Pre-fattening	2	3	2	3	2	2	0	2	2	3	2	1	3	3	2	1	3	3	3	2	2,20	2	2	0,83	0,38	2,35	5,17
258. Flexible procedures vs. Acidification / Declumping	2	3	2	3	2	2	0	2	2	3	2	1	3	3	2	1	3	3	3	2	2,20	2	2	0,83	0,38	2,00	4,40
259. Flexible procedures vs. Acidification / Fattening	2	3	2	3	2	2	0	2	2	3	2	1	3	3	2	1	3	3	3	2	2,20	2	2	0,83	0,38	2,17	4,78
260. Flexible procedures vs. Acidification / Harvesting	2	3	2	3	2	2	0	2	2	3	2	2	3	3	2	1	3	3	3	2	2,25	2	2	0,79	0,35	1,91	4,30

Table 12. Matrix of results by expert in the Operational Environment dimension

- (1) Standard deviation: this is used to determine the dispersion of the data in its distribution with respect to the mean. The lower the value, the more grouped the data will be around the sample mean.
- (2) C.V. = Coefficient of variation. Ratio between the standard deviation and the sample mean. In our case we use it to estimate the degree of agreement between the answers of the different experts. The lower the value of the coefficient of variation, the greater the concordance in the answers.
- (3) Weighted mean: Result of multiplying the "Mean" by the "Mean Risk Score". It provides a weighted average according to the degree of risk of the scenario on which the performance of the corresponding resilience factor is being evaluated.

Mean ≥ 2: High contribution

1 ≤ Mean < 2: Medium contribution

0 ≤ Mean < 1: Low contribution

RESILIENCE FACTORS		RISK SCENARIOS												
		Air temperature / Collecting seed from the rock	Surface water temperature / collecting seed from the rope	Surface water temperature / Collecting seed from the rock	Surface water temperature / Pre-fattening	Surface water temperature / Fattening	Wind / Collecting seed from the rock	Acidification / Collecting seed from the rope	Acidification / Collecting seed from the rock	Acidification / seed tubing	Acidification / Pre-fattening	Acidification / Declumping	Acidification / Fattening	Acidification / Harvesting
GOVERNANCE	1.1 Training programs: Joint training initiatives aimed at regulatory authorities, the productive sector and other key agents on the challenges of climate change and maritime culture to provide them with tools and knowledge to implement effective adaptation strategies.	2,52	3,39	3,92	2,64	2,82	1,64	3,66	3,40	2,10	2,35	2,00	2,07	1,91
	1.2 Flexible management: Use of adaptive management principles, both by the public administration and the productive sector, to address uncertainty with a flexible and agile approach (e.g. iterative decision-making, incorporation of constant feedback and adjustment of assumptions according to the evolution of the scenarios).	3,27	4,30	4,61	3,62	3,86	2,58	4,03	4,29	3,00	3,64	2,90	3,15	2,77
	1.3 Marine spatial planning: Introduce into Maritime Spatial Planning Plans (MSPs) strategies that incorporate the assessment of potential impacts of climate change on mussel aquaculture and other maritime activities, with the aim of preventing conflicts and promoting sustainable coexistence between various sectors.	2,90	3,84	4,15	3,23	3,44	2,82	4,03	4,41	2,90	3,40	2,80	2,83	2,30
	1.4 Management of public-private funds: Assessment of the financial needs for the adaptation of the sector in order to efficiently create and manage funds of public-private origin that allow preventive actions to be carried out and/or to cover future contingencies.	2,90	3,84	3,69	2,64	2,92	2,11	3,03	3,28	2,20	2,47	2,10	2,28	2,10
R+D+I	2.1 Advanced scientific research: Development of specific innovative studies aimed at identifying patterns, projecting future scenarios and deepening the understanding of the impacts of climate change on the production process for informed decision-making based on scientific evidence.	4,49	5,99	5,88	4,89	5,22	3,52	6,30	6,18	4,30	4,93	4,40	4,46	3,73
	2.2 Improvement of exposure forecasts: Use of models to predict changes in the frequency and intensity of oceanic-meteorological variables to anticipate the level of exposure of each cultivation area, minimizing risks and improving the capacity to act.	3,83	5,09	5,18	4,11	4,38	3,21	5,17	5,17	3,60	4,11	3,50	3,80	3,25
	2.3 Applied biotechnology projects: Promotion of biotechnology applications aimed at the development of mussel strains that are more resistant to stressors associated with climate change, such as extreme weather events or increased frequency of toxic tides. This includes strategies such as selective breeding, genomic selection to preserve robustness, or genetic adaptation, among others.	2,34	4,30	3,69	3,62	3,86	2,19	5,04	4,16	3,70	4,34	3,60	3,91	3,16
	2.4 Development of new technologies: Development and implementation of advanced technological solutions that have innovative processes to promote flexibility, better environmental control and greater efficiency in the use of resources in a changing environment (e.g. smart buoys, remote sensors, drones or artificial intelligence-based systems for early warning).	2,99	4,52	3,92	3,72	3,97	2,50	4,79	4,29	3,40	3,76	3,30	3,37	2,97

Table 13. Weighted mean matrix. Governance and R+D+I dimensions.

Mean ≥ 2: High contribution

1 ≤ Mean < 2: Medium contribution

0 ≤ Mean < 1: Low contribution

RESILIENCE FACTORS		RISK SCENARIOS												
		Air temperature / Collecting seed from the rock	Surface water temperature / collecting seed from the rope	Surface water temperature / Collecting seed from the rock	Surface water temperature / Pre-fattening	Surface water temperature / Fattening	Wind / Collecting seed from the rock	Acidification / Collecting seed from the rope	Acidification / Collecting seed from the rock	Acidification / seed tubing	Acidification / Pre-fattening	Acidification / Declumping	Acidification / Fattening	Acidification / Harvesting
RISK MANAGEMENT	3.1 Multitrophic aquaculture: Diversification of production through the identification and use of possible synergies with species that are more resilient to climate change and extensive farming (macroalgae, crustaceans, etc.).	1,96	3,05	2,65	2,64	2,82	1,64	3,66	3,15	2,70	3,29	2,60	2,93	2,49
	3.2 Adapted insurance coverage: Underwriting insurance policies that provide adequate coverage for potential risks arising from climate change, in situations where it is not possible to take preventive measures.	1,87	2,37	2,19	2,15	2,19	1,64	2,65	2,77	1,90	2,23	1,80	1,96	2,01
	3.3 Ecosystem Approaches to Aquaculture (EEA): Strategies for integrating aquaculture into the context of the wider ecosystem in which it takes place, reducing disaster risk while promoting sustainable development, equity and resilience of interconnected socio-ecological systems.	3,46	4,86	4,72	4,11	4,38	3,05	5,42	5,17	3,90	4,58	3,80	4,13	3,73
	3.4 Emergency action plans: Design contingency plans with agile and predefined responses, adapted to extreme weather events, which help coordinate the authorities, the productive sector and other actors in order to minimize impacts and losses.	3,55	4,63	4,72	3,91	4,17	3,05	5,17	5,04	3,70	4,34	3,60	3,91	3,44
COLLABORATION	4.1 Intersectoral collaboration: Partnership with other actors in the productive sector, with the extractive fishing sector and with other complementary sectors for joint negotiation and alignment of actions in the face of possible risks.	3,83	4,75	5,18	3,23	3,34	3,05	4,54	5,04	2,80	3,17	2,70	2,93	2,68
	4.2 Interdisciplinary cooperation: Clear and accessible channels of communication between agents from different disciplines (biology, engineering, climatology, economics, administration, etc.) with the aim of seeking comprehensive solutions and coordinating adaptation measures to the impacts of climate change.	4,30	5,65	5,65	4,60	4,90	3,60	5,93	6,05	4,40	5,17	4,30	4,67	4,11
	4.3 International cooperation networks: Participation of sector actors in international cooperation networks to share information, resources, best practices and experiences on adaptation.	3,08	4,30	3,92	3,33	3,55	2,50	4,16	4,16	3,20	3,64	3,10	3,37	2,87
	4.4 Intra-sectoral collaboration: Creation of collaborative networks in which each cultivation area specialises in a specific phase of the production process, depending on the optimal climatic and meteorological conditions for that specific stage. E.g., some farming areas may focus on mussel farming, while others may specialize in fattening.	2,15	3,84	3,34	3,03	3,23	1,96	3,66	3,40	2,60	2,93	2,30	2,72	2,10

Table 14. Weighted mean matrix. Risk Management and Collaboration dimensions.

Mean ≥ 2: High contribution

1 ≤ Mean < 2: Medium contribution

0 ≤ Mean < 1: Low contribution

RESILIENCE FACTORS		RISK SCENARIOS												
		Air temperature / Collecting seed from the rock	Surface water temperature / collecting seed from the rope	Surface water temperature / Collecting seed from the rock	Surface water temperature / Pre-fattening	Surface water temperature / Fattening	Wind / Collecting seed from the rock	Acidification / Collecting seed from the rope	Acidification / Collecting seed from the rock	Acidification / seed tubing	Acidification / Pre-fattening	Acidification / Declumping	Acidification / Fattening	Acidification / Harvesting
OPERATIONAL ENVIRONMENT	5.1 Adaptation of infrastructures: Incorporation of new infrastructure, improvements to existing assets and nature-based solutions (e.g. creation of artificial reefs, integrated mariculture, restoration of seagrass meadows, etc.) focused on increasing resilience to the impacts of climate change on the aquaculture process.	2,80	3,96	3,92	3,33	3,55	2,58	4,29	4,29	2,80	3,17	2,70	2,93	2,58
	5.2 Monitoring and warning systems: Adoption of real-time monitoring and early warning systems that allow the monitoring of farm conditions, agile response to adverse events and changing conditions (oceanic-meteorological phenomena, pests, predators, etc.).	4,02	5,09	5,18	4,30	4,70	3,52	5,55	5,42	3,90	4,58	3,90	4,35	3,83
	5.3 Improvement of production techniques: Adoption of technology monitoring processes aimed at identifying the best available practices, as well as the development and incorporation of innovative techniques and solutions that strengthen the adaptation of operations to the challenges of climate change.	3,65	5,09	4,84	4,21	4,49	3,05	5,55	5,17	4,40	4,93	4,20	4,46	4,02
	5.4 Flexible procedures: Operating procedures, based on the principles of continuous improvement and the circular economy, with the ability to adapt to changing conditions and new production needs that allow a better use of both resources and products, in a sustainable cycle.	4,39	5,65	5,53	4,79	5,11	3,68	6,18	5,93	4,40	5,17	4,40	4,78	4,30

Table 15. Weighted mean matrix. Operational Environment dimension.

05 DELPHI 2: RESILIENCE GAPS - RESULTS

Ranking of the 14 highest-priority resilience factors*, ordered by the average score of their contribution to adaptation

N	Resilience factor ranking	Dimension	Risk Scenarios (ordered by priority)														
			1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13		
1	Advanced scientific research	R+D+I	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○		○	
2	Flexible procedures	Operational environment	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	
3	Interdisciplinary cooperation	Collaboration	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	
4	Intersectoral collaboration	Collaboration	○	○		○	○										
5	Monitoring and alert systems	Operational environment	○	○	○	○	○	○	○				○		○		
6	Improvement of exposure forecasts	R+D+I	○	○	○	○	○		○					○			
7	Emergency action plans	Risk management	○	○	○	○	○		○								
8	Ecosystem approach to aquaculture (EEA)	Risk management	○	○	○	○	○	○	○				○				
9	Improvement of production techniques	Operational environment	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○	○			
10	New Technologies Development	R+D+I	○				○										
11	Flexible management	Governance	○	○		○	○										
12	Infrastructure adaptation	Operational environment	○														
13	International Cooperation Networks	Collaboration	○	○			○										
14	Marine space planning	Governance				○											

Legend	
Scenario 1	Acidification / Collecting seed from the rope
Scenario 2	Acidification / Collecting seed from the rock
Scenario 3	Acidification / Pre-fattening
Scenario 4	Surface water temp. / Collecting seed from the rock
Scenario 5	Surface water temp. / collecting seed from the rope
Scenario 6	Acidification / Fattening
Scenario 7	Surface water temp. / Fattening
Scenario 8	Acidification / seed tubing
Scenario 9	Acidification / Declumping
Scenario 10	Surface water temp. / Pre-fattening
Scenario 11	Acidification / Harvesting
Scenario 12	Air temp. / Collecting seed from the rock
Scenario 13	Wind / Collecting seed from the rock

This figure presents the resilience factors with the highest contribution to face the effects of the priority risk scenarios posed by climate change.

The scenario 13 (Wind over the seed on the rock), although it is the lowest priority scenario, presents a coverage gap. According to the experts, the resilience factors that can contribute most to minimising it are “Flexible procedures” or “Interdisciplinary cooperation”, but with a moderate contribution (means equals to 3.68 and 3.60, respectively).

Figure 22. Ranking of the 14 highest-priority resilience factors and their contribution to the priority risk scenarios

*Selection criteria:

- To measure the level of contribution of the resilience factors to the risk scenarios, the average of the experts' responses has been used, taking 4.0 as the minimum threshold.
- To assess consensus, the coefficient of variation was used, with a maximum threshold of 0.50.

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06 Assessment of adaptive capacity

6.1 Expert panel distribution

6.2 Questionnaire

6.3 Results

[General index](#)

Stakeholder groups	Experts
Science / Academia	4
Government	4
Society	4
Environment	4
Economy	4
	20

Gender	Total	%
Men	10	50,00%
Women	10	50,00%
	20	100%

Once the risks and the resilience factors were identified and the level of impact have been measured, a **final assessment questionnaire** was conducted on the **sector's adaptive capacities** with the aim of evaluate the extent to which the mussel sector in Galicia has the necessary tools to cope with the impacts of climate change.

As has been carried out previously in the RI methodology, for the self-assessment of adaptive capacity **key players involved in the case study region** were identified.

20 experts have been invited, of which **100%** of them have been engaged to complete their participation in all three rounds.

These 20 experts were distributed in a **perfect balanced proportion**, not only among the five **stakeholder groups**, but also in terms of gender since the **full parity** has been achieved.

Table 16. Expert panel distribution in the questionnaire on sector capacities for adaptation

This questionnaire was conducted in **Microsoft Forms** and also in Spanish, as it was addressed to local experts.

A **Likert scale (0-10)** was used to score the level of performance of **52 statements**, all related to the **20 resilience factors**, where 0 meant “strongly disagree” and 10 meant “totally agree”.

It was divided into **five sections**, corresponding to the five dimensions of resilience factors.

Figure 23. Online questionnaire for the adaptive capacities assessment.

RESULTS FROM THE ASSESSMENT OF ADAPTIVE CAPACITY

20 experts

52 statements assessed

This figure shows the performance, from highest to lowest, of the 20 resilience factors in the adaptive capacity questionnaire.

Only three factors score more than 50%: "Training programmes", "Monitoring and warning systems" and "Advanced scientific research". On the other hand, with the lowest level of performance, is "Emergency action plans".

Figure 24. Level of performance of the resilience factors for the adaptation of the mussel aquaculture sector in Galicia to the effects of climate change.

06 ASSESSMENT OF ADAPTIVE CAPACITY - RESULTS

Level of performance by resilience dimensions

The 5 dimensions of the adaptation factors are presented in order of highest to lowest performance (from left to right and from top to bottom).

The **Governance** dimension stands out with two key adaptation factors scoring over 50%: "Marine Spatial Planning" and "Training Programs", especially the latter with 68%, the highest among the 20 factors. In the **operational area**, "Monitoring and warning systems" stands out with 57%. **R&D&I** maintains a balanced performance, with "Advanced scientific research" in the lead with 52%. Factors in the **Collaboration** block hover around 50%, urging the need for specialised collaboration networks. Finally, **Risk Management** has the lowest performance, with "Emergency response plans" at 28%.

Figure 25. Level of performance of the adaptation factors by resilience dimensions.

06 ASSESSMENT OF ADAPTIVE CAPACITY - RESULTS

Expert prioritisation and current performance

This figure shows the resilience factors, ranked in order of importance in terms of their contribution to adaptation, and the score obtained after the expert panel's assessment of their performance in the sector.

The results seem to suggest that there is some **room for improvement** in the climate change adaptation factors most highlighted by the experts.

If we focus on the upper half of the graph, where the factors with the greatest contribution to adaptation are found, we can see that only "Advanced scientific research" and "Monitoring and warning systems" exceed a performance level of 50%, while "Emergency action plans" have the lowest performance level, with 27.5%.

Figure 26. Expert prioritisation of the resilience factors and their current level of performance.

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07 Resilience Index final results

7.1 Introduction

7.2 RI calculation process in a nutshell

7.3 Resilience Index results

7.4 Co-creation of a tentative roadmap for adaptation

 [General index](#)

In this section, the final **calculations of the synthetic resilience index** are described and presented (section 7.2).

To represent the results obtained, a **dashboard** has been designed (section 7.3). This dashboard does not only display the overall **margin for improvement**, but it also presents the margin for improvement in each of the **5 dimensions of the 20 resilience factors** identified.

This tool points out **where it is most efficient to focus efforts** for adaptive capacity, providing valuable information for improvement proposals.

These results were presented to stakeholders in May 2024 in a participatory workshop to prioritize a set of actions based on the insights gained from the IR (section 8), resulting in a tentative roadmap for adaptation for the mussel sector in Galicia.

Figure 27. RI calculation process.

$$RI = \beta_{RF1}RF_1 + \beta_{RF2}RF_2 + \beta_{RF3}RF_3 + \dots + \beta_{RF_n}RF_n$$

$$RI = 165 * 48,49\% + 223 * 47,20\% + 179 * 34,49\% + 201 * 43,91\% + 232 * 48,47\%$$

Dimension 1. Governance	Dimension 2. R+D+I	Dimension 3. Risk Management	Dimension 4. Collaboration	Dimension 5. Operational environment
----------------------------	-----------------------	---------------------------------	-------------------------------	---

RI = 447
(out of 1000)

In the next section, the scores by each dimension and resilience factor are presented in both formats, as a dashboard and individually by dimension.

Once the results have been transferred to the model, we obtained a **synthetic index** that expresses the existing **margin for improvement**, multiplying the weight given by the experts to the resilience factors by the performance level of the mussel aquaculture sector, defined by the scores in the final assessment of adaptive capacity.

The sector shows a total score of **447 resilience points** out of 1000.

DECISION MAKING ASSISTANCE TOOL

Resilience Index

Resilience index strategy roadmap (see section 8)

Figure 28. RI results dashboard.

Figure 29. RI total result and results by dimension.

Figure 30. RI results for the Governance dimension

Figure 31. RI results for the R&D&I dimension

Figure 32. RI results for the Risk Management dimension.

Figure 33. RI results for the Collaboration dimension.

Figure 34. RI results for the Operational Environment dimension.

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08 Priority lines of action

8.1 Selection of priority resilience factors based on the RI results

8.2 Definition of priority lines of action

8.3 Workshop: tentative roadmap for adaptation

8.4 Stakeholders' perceptions of RI

[General index](#)

SELECTION CRITERIA:

- Weight in RI > 50 points
- Performance < 50%

Figure 35 shows two attributes of the resilience factors:

- On the left, the graph shows the weight of each resilience factor in the overall formula measured in points out of the total 1000.
- On the right, the graph shows the actual level of performance of the sector in each of the resilience factors.

Figure 35. Resilience factors weight and performance.

In order to draw a strategic roadmap for adaptation, the factors with the greatest potential to increase resilience but with the most room for improvement were prioritized. That is, those with a weight of more than 50 points and a performance level of less than 50% were selected (bars highlighted in blue and orange).

Based on literature review and previous feedback from stakeholders, the 6 priority resilience factors were transformed into 6 specific action lines. In addition, each line was further broken down into 4 specific solutions, creating a set of 24 specific proposals to be considered (see next page).

PRIORITY RESILIENCE FACTORS
1. Flexible procedures
2. Interdisciplinary cooperation
3. Improved production techniques
4. Ecosystem approaches to aquaculture (EEA)
5. Improved exposure forecasting
6. Emergency response plans

Table 17. Priority resilience factors.

LINES OF ACTION	
	1. Flexibilization and adaptation of operational procedures.
	2. Establishment of clear and accessible channels of communication between actors from different disciplines.
	3. Improvement, development and incorporation of innovative techniques and solutions in the productive environment.
	4. Integration of aquaculture in the context of the wider ecosystem in which it takes place.
	5. Improvement of models for predicting changes in the frequency and intensity of oceanic-meteorological variables.
	6. Design of contingency plans and action plans for emergencies caused by meteorological events.

Table 18. Lines of action

LINES OF ACTION		PROPOSALS
	1. Flexibilization and adaptation of operational procedures.	1.1. Review operational procedures and formalities to eliminate those with low added value, thus achieving an agile structure that is adaptable to the changing environment.
		1.2. Implement systems for the continuous review of operational procedures, protocols and closures.
		1.3. Adopt a circularity and sustainability approach in the business model to improve resilience and operational efficiency.
		1.4. Promote technological innovation for proactive adaptation of operations.
	2. Establishment of clear and accessible channels of communication between actors from different disciplines.	2.1. Encourage participatory initiatives that favor direct and effective coordination and communication between professionals and actors in the sector.
		2.2. Use shared technological systems to improve digital information flows along the supply chain.
		2.3. Promote cooperation between the productive sector and the scientific community for the assessment of vulnerabilities and the search for solutions.
		2.4. Incorporate an integrated and coordinated approach between professionals from different disciplines for the implementation of adaptation measures.
	3. Improvement, development and incorporation of innovative techniques and solutions in the productive environment.	3.1. Design a technology watch and competitive intelligence plan on best adaptation practices.
		3.2. Promote the participation of producers in new projects for the development and implementation of innovative adaptation solutions for operations.
		3.3. Diversify the exploitation and adaptation of the business model with the objective of reducing vulnerability.
		3.4. Provide technical assistance to facilitate the adoption of state-of-the-art technologies for a more efficient adaptation of the sector.
	4. Integration of aquaculture in the context of the wider ecosystem in which it takes place.	4.1. Incorporating nature-based solutions as a crop protection measure.
		4.2. Ensure sector participation in cross-sectoral climate change adaptation bodies of the National Climate Change Adaptation Plan at the national or sub-national level.
		4.3. Use integrated aquaculture techniques that combine mussel production with the farming of other species.
		4.4. Identify and minimize indirect impacts on the environment in which they operate.
	5. Improvement of models for predicting changes in the frequency and intensity of oceanic-meteorological variables.	5.1. Develop and adopt detailed analytical forecasting tools to anticipate the needs of future events.
		5.2. Strengthen the collection of climate and ocean-meteorological data through the development of affordable and easily deployable sensor technology.
		5.3. Establish protocols for systematic assessment of post-event damage to allow for improvements in prevention models
		5.4. Develop prediction and monitoring models that take into account the interaction with other sub-sectors, the geographical distribution of crops and the information needs of local producers.
	6. Design of contingency plans and action plans for emergencies caused by meteorological events.	6.1. Establish mutual aid agreements with neighboring farms to provide support operations and the design of protocols for joint action.
		6.2. Design coordinated and adapted contingency plans for severe weather events.
		6.3. Define thresholds of production impact for response activation.
		6.4. Schedule periodic drills on possible risk events.

Table 19. Lines of action and proposals

On 24th of May 2024 an in-person workshop co-organized by CETMAR, UVIGO and FEUGA was held in Vilagarcía de Arousa (Galicia, Spain) under the title "*Solutions for adaptation to climate change in the Galician mussel sector - Resilience Index -*". A total of 28 persons (20 participants and 8 organizers), representatives of the quintuple helix (Administration, research, society, the environment and the productive sector) in the mussel sector have participated.

The attendees received information on key climate risks and their impacts on Galicia, findings of the resilience index for the mussel aquaculture and the six priority areas targeted to increase the adaptive capacity of the sector. For the discussion, **three heterogeneous stakeholder groups of 5-6 participants** were formed. Each group had a moderator and a rapporteur. The main phases of the dynamic were:

1. Reading and joint understanding by groups of the lines of action and proposed solutions.
2. Individual reflexion work to identify the 12 most important solutions and of these, the 6 most urgent.
3. Transfer of their selection to the 6 panels (one for each priority line) shared and visible to all participants.

The results of the voting, shown on the following pages, were shared with stakeholders at the end of the workshop and are available to the sector as a starting point for defining a common and agreed future roadmap, thus guiding the future actions needed to strengthen the resilience of the sector.

+info on TransformAr blog post: <https://transformar.eu/climate-change-adaptation-solutions-in-the-mussel-sector-of-galicia/>

Figure 36. Number of votes by urgency, importance and total votes of workshop attendees on resilience index results.

The results presented on figure 36 are based on the opinion of the participants. This results represent a proposed set of actions prioritized by importance and urgency. It provides a starting point for the definition of a specific future action plan.

The results seem to suggest that **action line 5** would be considered of high importance and urgency (61 votes), with proposal 5.2, focused on the reinforcement of climate and ocean-meteorological data collection with affordable and easy-to-implement sensors, being the one with the highest priority of all the proposed panel (22 total votes, 11 of importance and 11 of urgency).

The highest priority lines after line 5 would be 2 and 3 (48 votes each), where proposals 2.2 (18 votes) and 3.4 (17 votes) stand out, which refer to improving the flow of digital information along the supply chain and providing technical assistance to facilitate the adoption of cutting-edge technologies that favour a more efficient adaptation of the sector.

This analysis suggests that participants see improving climate change prediction and response capabilities as a priority, as well as fostering innovation and collaboration in the sector.

In figure 37, the horizontal axis (X) represents the degree of importance of the 17 most voted proposals in view of the votes received. The vertical axis (Y) represents the degree of urgency. Each green dot on the graph corresponds to one or more specific proposals. The labels next to each dot indicate the number of the proposal. The position of each dot on the graph indicates how important and urgent each proposal is considered.

This graph provides a clear visualization of what might be the most urgent and important actions among those proposed in this workshop and can serve as a reference to guide strategic planning for climate change adaptation in mussel aquaculture.

The highest priority proposals, those in the upper right corner of the graph, are proposed as the main focus for immediate action (see detail in the next page), while the other proposals should be addressed in the short to medium term to ensure comprehensive and effective adaptation.

Figure 37. Scatterplot of the relationship between Importance and Urgency

Figure 38. Tentative roadmap with the 5 highest priority proposals

In view of the results of the resilience index after expert consultation and stakeholder voting, the implementation of these proposals should increase significantly the level of resilience to the effects of climate change in the mussel aquaculture sector in Galicia (Spain). Once these actions have been implemented, the order of prioritization of additional proposals could be followed to keep increasing the level of resilience.

At the end of the session, participants were asked about their perception of the Resilience index results and the proposals derived from them.

The majority of participants (72%) reported an **increase in their awareness** to varying degrees after learning about the resilience index results. **The resilience index information is largely considered useful or very useful** by the majority of participants for identifying risk scenarios, strategic areas of action, and prioritizing solutions. A significant majority (94%) of participants **intend to incorporate the findings of the resilience index into their future decision-making processes** regarding climate change adaptation.

Therefore, the survey indicates a **positive impact of the resilience index on awareness, perceived usefulness, and future decision-making** among the stakeholder's representatives attending the workshop.

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon H2020 innovation action programme under grant agreement 101036683.